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Analysis of Healthy Aging Determinants in Europe to
improve Italy's Elderly Support

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	3
1.1 The “Old Age” Concept.....	4
1.2 Global Aging Population and its Determinants	5
1.2.1 Fertility.....	6
1.2.2 Life Expectancy and Healthy Life Years	10
1.3 The World Health Organization’s “Healthy Aging” Concept.....	12
1.4 Literature Review	15
1.5 Research Question.....	20
2. Data Analysis: Methodology.....	22
2.1 Data Acquisition	22
2.2 Data Preparation.....	25
2.2.1 Data Cleaning.....	25
2.2.2 Healthy Aging Index Construction.....	26
2.2.3 Descriptive Analysis of the Healthy Aging Index.....	30
2.3 Model Training and Testing.....	32
3. Data Analysis: Findings.....	38
3.1 Logistic Regression	40
3.2 Random Forest.....	41
3.3 Light Gradient Boosting Machine	42
3.4 SHAP Value for Light Gradient Boosting Machine Results Interpretation.....	43
4. Policy Insights for Italy’s Elderly Support	52
4.1 An Overview of the Italian Long Term Care Services.....	52
4.2 LTC Services Coverage Rate and Private Caregiving.....	54
4.3 Policy Insights for the Italian LTC System	57
4.3.1 Actual Services	60
4.3.2 Cash Transfers.....	66

5. Conclusions.....	71
6. Bibliography	73
7. Acknowledgements.....	80

1. Introduction

Aging Population is a growing global phenomenon driven by falling fertility rates and increasing life expectancy. The world is experiencing an unprecedented and sustained change in the age structure of its population that is changing the socio-demographic structure of countries and needs to be tackled by governments with ad-hoc policies.

At a biological level aging consists of the accumulation of molecular and cellular damage that over time results in a decrease of physiological abilities and a decline in the individual's capacities. The aging process is not linear as some of its mechanisms are strongly influenced by the environment and behavior of the individual.

The Elderly can positively contribute to society in many ways if they are in good health conditions. As people aged 65 or older are rapidly becoming a wider share of the population in all European countries, governments will need to develop and redesign the services directed to them to support their aging and, therefore, their contribution to society.

The aim of this Thesis is to identify the individual and macroeconomic variables impacting the well-being of the population aged 65 or older in Europe, based on the "Healthy Aging" concept of the World Health Organization, to provide Policy Suggestions to increase the quality of life of the elderly population in Italy.

The Thesis is divided into four Chapters: Introduction, Data Analysis: Methodology, Data Analysis: Findings, Policy Insights for Italy's Elderly Support. The first Chapter presents the phenomenon of Aging Population and the "Healthy Aging" concept of the World Health Organization, alongside a review of the Literature in the field of study of quality of life in the elderly population. The second Chapter describes the three data analysis methods (Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Light Gradient Boosting Machine) used on the easySHARE dataset for individual variables and the data of the World Bank for the macroeconomic variables. The third Chapter presents the results of the data analysis that are analyzed with the SHAP values to draw relevant findings. The fourth and last Chapter presents an overview of the Italian Policies and Long Term Care Services to assist the elderly population and provides six Policy Suggestions to improved the Healthy Aging of the elderly population in Italy.

1.1 The “Old Age” Concept

The elderly population is a definition that comprises those persons that are in the later part of their life. There is not a universal definition of the age at which an individual becomes “old” because the life expectancy and aging conditions differ widely across the globe. The United Nations usually define people aged 65 or older as the elderly population. However, the concept of elderly population is more related to the gradual loss of physical strength and mental health that leads to a less active life and a less active contribution to society. In most developed countries as Europe and the United States of America, the concept of “old person” comes with being eligible for retirement, which is often between 60 and 65 years old. However, in less developed countries as Africa, the World Health Organization (WHO) often uses 55 years old to distinguish between adults and elderly.

The definition of elderly population has consistently changed over the years and continues to change. In the last years, more than one Gerontological and Geriatrics Society has proposed to shift the definition to people aged 75 or older, especially in the “world oldest countries”: Japan and Italy.

During the 63rd National Congress of the Italian Society of Gerontology and Geriatrics (SIGG) held in Rome in November 2018, a new definition of elderly was proposed that set the threshold at 75 years old, considered more suitable to the current physical and mental conditions, the demographic situation of the Italian population and, in general, the psychophysical conditions of subjects belonging to high-income countries. Indeed, thanks to the medical advancement and the good living conditions of many countries people at 65 years are still robust and active. Before this, in May 2017 the Joint Committee of Japan Gerontological Society and the Japan Geriatrics Society published a paper that also proposed to change the definition of old age at 75 years or older. The joint committees, after an evaluation started in 2013 and concluded after 3 years that analyzed various data on the physical and psychological health of the elderly, concluded that “a phenomenon of “rejuvenation” has been seen in which the appearance of changes in physical function as a result of aging, including gait speed and grip strength, have been delayed by 5-10 years among the elderly at present compared with 10–20 years ago” (Yasuyoshi Ouchi et al., 2017, p.1).

1.2 Global Aging Population and its Determinants

In 2020 the number of people aged 65 or older was 727 million. This figure is expected to more than double over the next three decades, reaching over 1.5 billion in 2050. The world population is expected to reach 9.8 billion in 2050, meaning that the share of the global population aged 65 or older is expected to grow from 9,3% in 2020 to around 16% by 2050. All regions are expected to see an increase in the size of their older population between 2020 and 2050 (United Nations: World Population Aging, 2020).

In 1980 children under 10 years substantially outnumbered elderly persons aged over 60. But by 2030 the global population aged 60 years or older is expected to surpass the one of children aged 0-9. The forecasts indicate that in 2050 there will be more older persons aged 60 or older than children (0-9 years) and adolescents (10-24 years). Moreover, the number of people aged 80 or older, usually defined as “oldest old”, is projected to triple by 2050, increasing from 137 million to 425 million (Figure 1) (United Nations: World Population Aging, 2017).

Figure 1 - Global Population by age group in 1980, 2017, 2030, and 2050

Global population by broad age group, in 1980, 2017, 2030 and 2050

Data source: United Nations (2017). World Population Prospects: the 2017 Revision.

Although the process of population aging is present worldwide, it is most advanced in Europe and North America, where in 2017 more than one in five persons was aged 60 or older. “In 2050, older persons are expected to account for 35 percent of the population in Europe, 28 percent in Northern America, 25 percent in Latin America and the Caribbean, 24 percent in Asia, 23 percent in Oceania and 9 percent in Africa” (Figure 2) (United Nations: World Population Aging, 2017, p.6).

Figure 2- Population Aged over 60 by region

Percentage of population aged 60 years or over by region, from 1980 to 2050

Data source: United Nations (2017). World Population Prospects: the 2017 Revision.

1.2.1 Fertility

Over the recent decades, the global fertility rate has sharply declined from 3.2 births per woman in 1990 to 2.5 in 2019. “The global level of fertility is expected to reach 2.2 live births per woman in 2050 and 1.9 in 2100” (United Nations, 2020). The level required for populations with low mortality rates to have a growth rate of zero, in the long run, is 2.1 live birth per woman, and today close to half of the global population lives in a country where fertility is below this threshold. Fertility and its declining trends vary largely across countries and regions in the world (Figure 3 and 4). Figure 4 shows how “in Australia and New Zealand and Europe and Northern America, fertility in 1990 was already below 2.0 births per woman, and it remains so today, with 1.8 births per woman, on average, in Australia and New Zealand in 2019, and 1.7 in Europe and Northern America” (United Nations, 2020).

Figure 3 - Fertility Rate by Country or Area in 2019
Total fertility rate by country or area, 2019

Source: United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2019a). *World Population Prospects 2019*.

Figure 4 - Fertility Rate by Region in 2019

Total fertility rate by region, estimates and projections, 1950-2100

Source: United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2019a). *World Population Prospects 2019*.

Europe is among the countries with the lowest fertility rates in the world. In 2019 4.2 million babies were born in the EU (Figure 5), an average of 1.53 live births per woman (compared to 1.54 in 2018).

Figure 6 shows that “fertility rates steadily declined from the mid-1960s through to the turn of the century in the EU Member States. However, at the beginning of the 2000s, the total fertility rate in the EU displayed signs of rising again. This development stopped in 2010 and a subsequent decline was observed through to a relatively low in 2013, followed by a slight increase up to 2016 and another decrease since” (Eurostat, 2021).

Figure 5 - Number of Live Births in EU 1961-2019

Figure 6 - Fertility Rate in EU 1961-2019

Among the EU Member States total fertility rates range from 1.14 in Malta to 1.86 in France (Figure 7 and 8). Italy is the third-worst country in these terms with only 1.27 live births per woman, followed only by Spain (1.23), and Malta (1.14).

Figure 7 - EU Member States Fertility Rates 1960-2019

Total fertility rate, 1960-2019
(live births per woman)

	1960	1970	1980	1990	2000	2001	2010	2017	2018	2019
EU (*)						1.43	1.57	1.56	1.54	1.53
Belgium	2.54	2.25	1.80	1.62	1.67	1.67	1.86	1.65	1.62	1.58
Bulgaria	2.31	2.17	2.06	1.82	1.26	1.21	1.57	1.56	1.56	1.58
Czechia	2.09	1.92	2.08	1.90	1.15	1.15	1.51	1.69	1.71	1.71
Denmark	2.57	1.95	1.55	1.67	1.77	1.74	1.87	1.75	1.73	1.70
Germany					1.38	1.35	1.39	1.57	1.57	1.54
Estonia	1.98	2.17	2.02	2.05	1.36	1.32	1.72	1.59	1.67	1.66
Ireland	3.78	3.85	3.21	2.11	1.89	1.94	2.05	1.77	1.75	1.71
Greece	2.23	2.40	2.23	1.39	1.25	1.25	1.48	1.35	1.35	1.34
Spain			2.22	1.36	1.22	1.23	1.37	1.31	1.26	1.23
France					1.89	1.90	2.03	1.89	1.87	1.86
Croatia						1.46	1.55	1.42	1.47	1.47
Italy (†)	2.40	2.38	1.64	1.33	1.26	1.25	1.46	1.32	1.29	1.27
Cyprus				2.41	1.64	1.57	1.44	1.32	1.32	1.33
Latvia					1.25	1.22	1.36	1.69	1.60	1.61
Lithuania		2.40	1.99	2.03	1.39	1.29	1.50	1.63	1.63	1.61
Luxembourg (‡)	2.29	1.97	1.50	1.60	1.76	1.66	1.63	1.39	1.38	1.34
Hungary	2.02	1.88	1.91	1.87	1.32	1.31	1.25	1.54	1.55	1.55
Malta			1.99	2.02	1.68	1.48	1.36	1.26	1.23	1.14
Netherlands	3.12	2.57	1.60	1.62	1.72	1.71	1.79	1.62	1.59	1.57
Austria	2.69	2.29	1.65	1.46	1.36	1.33	1.44	1.52	1.47	1.46
Poland (‡)				2.06	1.37	1.31	1.41	1.48	1.46	1.44
Portugal (‡)	3.16	3.01	2.25	1.56	1.55	1.45	1.39	1.38	1.42	1.43
Romania			2.43	1.83	1.31	1.27	1.59	1.78	1.78	1.77
Slovenia				1.46	1.26	1.21	1.57	1.62	1.60	1.61
Slovakia	3.04	2.41	2.32	2.09	1.30	1.20	1.43	1.52	1.54	1.57
Finland	2.72	1.83	1.63	1.78	1.73	1.73	1.87	1.49	1.41	1.35
Sweden		1.92	1.68	2.13	1.54	1.57	1.98	1.78	1.76	1.71
Iceland		2.81	2.48	2.30	2.08	1.95	2.20	1.71	1.71	1.74
Liechtenstein					1.57	1.52	1.40	1.44	1.58	1.48
Norway		2.50	1.72	1.93	1.85	1.78	1.95	1.62	1.56	1.53
Switzerland	2.44	2.10	1.55	1.58	1.50	1.38	1.52	1.52	1.52	1.48
Montenegro							1.70	1.78	1.76	1.77
North Macedonia					1.88	1.73	1.56	1.43	1.42	1.34
Albania							1.63	1.48	1.37	
Serbia					1.48	1.58	1.40	1.49	1.49	1.52
Turkey							2.04	2.07	1.99	1.88

(*) 2010, 2017 and 2019: break in series.

(†) 2019: break in series.

(‡) 2017: break in series.

(§) 2000 and 2010: break in series.

Source: Eurostat (online data code: demo_find)

eurostat

Figure 8 - EU Member States Fertility Rate Map in 2019

1.2.2 Life Expectancy and Healthy Life Years

In the last decades, there has been a significant increase in life expectancy worldwide. This is the result of the reduction in infant mortality from infectious diseases, especially during birth and childhood, in low and middle-income countries, and of declining mortality rates in the elderly population in high-income countries.

Although life expectancy at birth is in Europe one of the highest in the world (81 years in total - 78.5 years for males and 84 for females in 2019) (World Bank Data, 2020) too many are still the years lived with severe or moderate limitations in daily activities.

The older population can positively contribute to society in many ways, however, this largely depends on the health conditions of these individuals. If people are experiencing those “extra years” in good health their ability to support their family and community will have few limits, but if these years are instead dominated by mental and physical decline their contribution to society may be impossible. Although it is often assumed that increasing longevity is accompanied by better health conditions in elderly life this is not always the case.

The Healthy Life Years Indicator (HLY), also known as “Disability-Free Life Expectancy” or “Sullivan's Index”, is a measure of the remaining years a person is expected to live free of disability. The Index in Europe is calculated by the Eurostat in the Eurostat EU-Statistics on Income and Living Conditions Survey (EU-SILC) to provide a synthetic measure of the health expectancy between countries. The HLY Indicator is estimated at birth (HLY at birth) and at age 65 (HLY at age 65).

The data produced by Eurostat shows clear differences between the Member States in life expectancy without disabilities. In 2019, the HLY at birth for European Union was estimated at 65.1 for women and 64.2 for men (Figure 9).

Figure 9- Eurostat Healthy Life Years at Birth for European Countries

“Across the EU Member States, life expectancy at birth for women in 2019 ranged between 78.8 years in Bulgaria to 86.7 years in Spain; a difference of 7.9 years. A similar comparison for men shows that the lowest level of life expectancy in 2019 was recorded in Latvia 70.9 years and the highest in Sweden 81.5 years; a range of 10.6 years. Life expectancy for women in the EU was, on average, 5.5 years longer than that for men in 2019. However, most of these additional years tend to be lived with activity limitations. Indeed, at just 0.9 years difference in favor of women, the gender gap was considerably smaller in terms of healthy life years (HLY Indicator) than it was for overall life expectancy. Men, therefore, tend to spend a greater proportion of their somewhat shorter lives free from activity limitations.” (Eurostat Report on Healthy Life Years at Birth, 2019).

Italian men (both males and females) are characterized in the European framework for having the highest longevity of 83 years, alongside France, Malta, Norway, Spain, and Sweden (World Bank Data, 2019), compared to the European Union average of 81 years (World Bank Data, 2019), but a lower value than some European countries with similar life expectancy in the percentage of years lived free from disability (82% in Italy, 88% in Malta, 84% in Spain, and 88% in Sweden). Italian men, therefore, tend to spend a shorter portion of their longer life free from disabilities compared to other European countries.

1.3 The World Health Organization's "Healthy Aging" Concept

The term "Healthy Aging" is widely used in academic and policy circles to "identify a positive disease-free state that distinguishes between healthy and unhealthy individuals". The concept is particularly relevant in the elderly population where there are often one or more conditions that if well controlled can have little impact on the quality of life of individuals. In framing a strategy for bettering the support of the elderly through the public health system, the concept of Healthy Aging is very valuable, since it frames the quality of life of the individual in a holistic sense that is based on life-course and functional perspectives.

The World Health Organization's "World Report on Aging and Health" of 2015 defines "Healthy Aging as the process of developing and maintaining the functional ability that enables well-being in older age" (World Report on Aging and Health, 2015, p.28). Functional Ability comprises health attributes that allow people to be and do what they have reason to value. Functional Ability "is made up of the intrinsic capacity of the individual, relevant environmental characteristics and the interactions between the individual and these characteristics" (World Report on Aging and Health, 2015, p.28). Below a detailed explanation of what intrinsic capacity and environment are and how their interaction creates the Functional Ability:

- **Intrinsic Capacity** "is the composite of all the physical and mental capacities of an individual" (World Report on Aging and Health, 2015, p.28), comprising the genetic inheritance everyone has at birth, the personal characteristic (that can be fixed such as sex and ethnicity but also flexible such as occupation, education background, gender and wealth) and health characteristics (such as physiological risk factors as high blood pressure, diseases, injuries, and broader geriatric syndromes). The interaction among the physical and mental capacities of the individual, from which he or she can draw, determine its intrinsic capacity. However, individuals cannot achieve the things they want and value just with their intrinsic capacity, because much of what they can do is determined by the interactions with the outside environment they live in.
- **Environments** "comprise all the factors in the extrinsic world that form the context of an individual's life. These include – from the micro-level to the

macro-level – home, communities, and the broader society. Within these environments are a range of factors, including the built environment, people and their relationships, attitudes, and values, health and social policies, the systems that support them, and the services that they implement...For example, older people with limitations in their physical capacity may still have the mobility they need if they use an assistive device and live close to public transport that provides access for people with disabilities. Another person with the same physical limitation but who lives in less enabling environments may find it much more difficult.” (World Report on Aging and Health, 2015, p.28-29).

Therefore, the concept of “Healthy Aging” considers the well-being of the individual in a very broad sense as a composite of good physical and mental health, happiness, satisfaction, and fulfillment.

Population aging is occurring alongside other “Environmental changes” in the social and economic sphere that are negatively impacting the living arrangement, and therefore the “Healthy Aging” of elderly people:

1. **Changes in the Patterns of Marriages:** Compared to the past there are fewer marriages, higher rates of divorce and some married couples do not live together for working or personal reasons. Figure 10 from Eurostat shows that the number of marriages per 1000 people is declining in the EU countries while the number of divorces is increasing, however, these trends seemed to have slowed down in recent years. The marriage rate in Italy in 2019 was the lowest of all the European Union with 3.1 marriages per 1000 habitants, followed by Portugal and Slovenia with 3.2.

Figure 10 - Number of marriages and divorces in the EU per 1000 persons

An increase of children born from unmarried couples and a decrease of children born from married couples have also been registered. “The proportion of live births outside marriage has shown an increasing trend in the past decades, almost doubling since 1993 when this data was first available in the EU at 17.7 %. In 2019 this proportion was estimated at 42.7 % which means that 57.3 % of children were born in marriage.” (Marriage and Divorce Statistics Eurostat, 2019). In several EU Member States, the extramarital births are outnumbering the birth inside marriages, as “France (where 61 % of births occurred outside marriage), Bulgaria (58.4 %), Slovenia (57.7 %), Portugal (56.8 %), Sweden (54.5 %), Denmark (54.1 %), Estonia (53.7 %), Belgium (52.6 %, 2018 data) and the Netherlands (52.4 %), as well as in Iceland (69.4 %) and Norway (57.6 %)” (Marriage and Divorce Statistics Eurostat, 2019). This trend signals that new family patterns are starting to occur alongside the more traditional pattern where children are born within marriages.

2. **Family Structures and Household composition:** In countries with historical data, as Western Europe and the United States of America, there has been a decline in multi-generational households. Indeed, most older persons live now alone or with their partner and in some cases with their unmarried children. Despite the traditional “big family” structure continues to exist, many countries in less developed regions are slowly experiencing a shift in the household composition towards smaller families. This is also impacted by the rise of Rural-to-Urban and International Migration, whose trends have globally increased in

the past decades. Cohabitation is common to support parent at older ages, often triggered by a decline in their physical or mental health that requires a family member to move with the elderly and take care of their personal needs. Cohabitation is also common to support the care of grandchildren and when there are periods of economic hardship, as was the case of the economic crisis of 2008 where intergenerational families reappeared in Europe and the United States of America.

In many countries, the living arrangements of older persons are associated with their economic well-being as well as with their physical and psychosocial health and life satisfaction (Ong and others, 2016; Zimmer and Das, 2014; Smith and others, 2018). Indeed, research has found an association between the living arrangements and the mortality risks of the elderly: those who live alone or in institutions have generally higher mortality rates than those living with their spouse or other family members.

1.4 Literature Review

The Literature Review encompasses all the relevant literature regarding the definition of Quality of Life in the Elderly Population and analysis on the determinants of Healthy Ageing, covering both qualitative and quantitative literature.

In the last years healthcare reforms, budget cuts, increasing regulations, and audit procedures have been common in many Western countries. As the population gets older the quality of life of older adults is gaining increasing importance in the evaluation and allocation of resources towards healthcare and social care services. "Maintenance of quality of life (QoL) is one the most important outcomes of care services for older adults. Several international action plans on aging endorse the importance of QoL and international interest in the measurement of QoL of older adults is growing. It is, however, not evident how QoL should be defined or how it should be assessed. The debate about the definition of QoL is conducted among researchers from various disciplines and overlaps with explorations of the concepts successful aging, subjective well-being, life satisfaction, and happiness" (Karen M. van Leeuwen, 2019, p.1).

There is a large set of possible frameworks to define the quality of life, the taxonomy conducted by Brown J, Bowling A, Flynn T. (2004, p.46) concludes that "QoL is inherently a dynamic, multi-level and complex concept, reflecting

objective, subjective, macro-societal, and micro-individual, positive and negative influences which interact together”.

Many theories have been proposed to define the quality of life, but a systematic overview of the opinion of the elderly on what quality of life means at old age was missing. The paper “What does quality of life mean to older adults? A thematic synthesis” (Karen M. van Leeuwen et al, 2019) aggregates findings up to the 28th November 2018 of a large number of qualitative studies to assess what quality of life is for older adults living at home. The review includes 48 qualitative studies representing the opinions of more than 3,400 older adults living at home in 11 Western countries. The results identified nine factors that shape the quality of life at old age: autonomy, role and activity, health perception, relationships, attitude and adaptation, emotional comfort, spirituality, home and neighborhood, and financial security.

These results are comparable and in line with previous studies as Stanley and Cheek (2003) and Brown et al. (2004).

Now that the concept of Quality of Life for the Elderly is defined, it is interesting to review the most recent studies that analyze the factors impacting Healthy Aging.

“Healthy ageing has been recognized as a priority policy objective in various countries, stimulated by reports of the European Union (EU) and the World Health Organization (WHO), with the objective to promote healthy ageing” (Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu, 2019, p.1).

The concept of Healthy Ageing is recognized as an important policy objective internationally but “evidence of which determinants or policies at country level may affect healthy aging is lacking” (Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu, 2019, p.1).

Policy makers, researchers, and health care workers look for determinants that may influence healthy aging (Windle G, 2012; World Health Organization, 2015; Cosco TD, Howse K, Brayne C, 2017). In the last decade three methods to assess healthy aging have been developed all using life expectancy at birth as starting point: “disability-free life expectancy, based on self-reported limitations in daily activities, self-related health life expectancy, based on self-perceived health, and disease-free life expectancy, based on the absence of specific diseases” (Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu, 2019, p.1)

Sadana et al. (2016) developed a framework in which contextual systems, that is for example social, political, and economic context, and health and social care, influence healthy aging both directly and indirectly through the vulnerability/strength of citizens (lifestyle, culture and environmental risk factors).

“Determinants of healthy ageing are found at individual level (health status, activity, resilience, social contacts, involvement) as well as at environmental/societal level (provisions for accessibility, housing, age-friendly communities, social security)” (Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu, 2019, p.1) in concordance with the World Health Organization definition of Healthy Aging as Functional Ability comprising Intrinsic Capacity, Environmental characteristics and the interactions between the individual and these characteristics.

“Researchers as well as policy documents formulate recommendations and proposals for (public health) interventions to promote healthy ageing (Zaidi A, 2014; World Health Organization, 2015; Acosta JD et al., 2018). The question is raised whether such recommendations are tailored to the needs of older adults. Whatever policy or intervention is recommended, empirical evidence to show the effectiveness of such policy or intervention, is absent.” (Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu, 2019, p.2)

The Healthy Aging Determinants present in policy documents include available and accessible health and social security services, sustainable pension system, healthy lifestyle, and social participation and cohesion (World Health Organization: World report on ageing and health, 2015).

“The EU documents mention determinants, which may influence healthy age directly or indirectly: access to health care, rural/urban/physical environment, transport and infra-structure, employment and working conditions, housing, education, social issues, pensions, poverty, justice, and violence and abuse” (Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu, 2019)

The key steps to promote healthy aging in the older population, according to the World Health Organization (2015) “World report on ageing and health”, are: Active participation of older persons in society, no age discrimination, and accessibility to public health and social services.

The EuroHealthNet Report (2012) “Healthy and active ageing” states that health policies for people aged 50 or older tend to focus on employments and the transition into retirement, and physical and social activities to stay active and socially connected after retirement. Moreover, the paper suggests that people aged 50 or older should “adopt good nutrition habits and engage in physical activity...utilise healthcare services, which are able to address their specific needs, on a regular basis....people in this age group are often ‘carers’ of youth and of older people, and may need assistance coping with these roles” (EuroHealthNet Report, 2012). The paper proposes a “Compendium of Good Practices” on these different topics on the basis of studies conducted across Europe addressing: Employment and the transition into retirement, Participation/social inclusion, including engagement in voluntary work and mental health, Life-long learning and e-inclusion, Physical activity and nutrition, Utilisation of health services and intake of medication, and Carers.

As the economic development and technological changes are rapidly upgrading in Europe, the possibility to use Data Analysis to support the identification of the determinants of Healthy Aging and with its results sustaining the development of a public Health System more tailored to the needs of the elderly is becoming a valid opportunity.

Several studies have been developed in this field in the last years, covering different methodologies and including different factors impacting Healthy Ageing. Here a detailed overview of the most recent studies in the field and how this Thesis stemmed from a gap in the literature is proposed.

There are a few studies that analyze empirically the relationships between determinants at national and individual level and healthy aging. These studies’ findings highlight various factors to be related to Healthy Aging: well-being, material resources, socioeconomic status, lifestyle, social involvement and participation, and self-rated health (Havenman Na, 2003; Peel Na, 2005; Cosco TD et al, 2014; Waldman Ka et al. 2015; Sowa A et al, 2016; McPhee JS et al., 2016; Sadana et al, 2016).

The paper “Determinants of Healthy Ageing in European Countries” of Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olariu (2019) performs a comparative study that explores the relationship between vulnerability, social cohesion, and resilience, and healthy aging in 31 European countries over data from 2013 or 2014 based on international data sets as Eurostat and the European Social Survey.

Vulnerability, social cohesion, and resilience are evaluated based on 10 indicators and defined as follows: “Vulnerability at national level indicates the proportion of citizens at risk for poverty and access to services. Social cohesion at national level describes the extent to which citizens are willing to accept each other. Resilience at national level includes national resources for citizens, which may support them to overcome adverse events.” (Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu, 2019, p.1)

The study concludes that “Vulnerability, social cohesion, and resilience are interconnected and relevant determinants of healthy ageing, which indicates that an integrated approach is needed to realize healthy ageing.” (Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu, 2019, p.1)

Interestingly, Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu (2019, p.1) highlight that “mean healthy ageing in the 31 European countries is 72.9 years; the difference between lowest and highest is over 15 years. Multiple correlation between the 3 components and healthy ageing explains 71% of the variance. Regression analysis shows a significant contribution of resilience and vulnerability as determinants of healthy ageing”. From the significant difference in terms of healthy aging years among the European Countries highlighted in this study, stemmed the idea of including in this Thesis a study at the European level to identify individual determinants that are impacting the Healthy Ageing of the population aged 65 or older.

A very recent study is the paper “Data Analysis Model Design of Health Service Monitoring System for China’s Elderly Population: The Proposal of the F-W Model Based on the Collaborative Governance Theory of Healthy Aging” of Liping Fu, Tao Teng, Yuhui Wang, and Lanping He (2020). The study analyzes through stepwise Logistic Regression which factors impact the healthy aging of individuals in China, using the public micro-panel data of the China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Survey (CHARLS), and propose an F-W (factors and weighs, also family and welfare) model to support the design and development of the Health Service Monitoring System (HSMS). “The outcomes can contribute with designing HSMS for different provinces and several different regions in China and leave a door open to improve the model and algorithm application for HSMS in the future studies” (Liping Fu et al., 2020, p.1).

Although the study does not cover the European Countries, as is the aim of this Thesis, it is interesting because it groups a wide range of independent variables into four

determinants of Healthy Aging: Physical Health, Ability of daily activities, Mental Health, and Social Participation. This methodology will be adapted and used in this Thesis on data from the Survey of Health, Aging and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), which is part of an Internal Cooperation project with other similar studies around the world, including CHARLS.

Therefore, the studies of Wim JA van den Heuvel and Marinela Olaroiu (2019) and of Liping Fu, Tao Teng, Yuhui Wang, and Lanping He (2020) have been the main source of inspiration for the methodology used in this Thesis.

This Thesis stemmed from the understanding of the importance of using Data Analysis to support the development and design of National Healthcare Services towards a model that can better support the needs of the elderly population based on the Healthy Ageing concept. An analysis of the determinants of the wellbeing of the elderly population in Europe, based on the Healthy Ageing concept of the World Health Organization and including a wide variety of independent variables at an individual level, with data from SHARE, and at a macroeconomic level, with data from the World Bank Data, was missing and this Thesis aims to cover this gap in the literature. Moreover, a focus on the Italian Healthcare Services and how it can be improved to support the elderly, based on relevant data findings, will be covered by this Thesis.

1.5 Research Question

Going on with the years all the countries will have to face the challenges of the socio-demographic changes of their population towards an older, and thus more fragile, society.

In this Thesis, the first goal is to identify the factors that impact the well-being of the elderly in the European countries using the Healthy Aging concept. Thus, the first Research Question is:

“Which factors impact the Healthy Aging of the Elderly Population in European countries?”

The analysis will encompass physical and mental health variables that can be impacted by Health and Social Policies, economic variables that can be impacted by General Public Policies, and demographics variables that are out of governmental

scope, by using different techniques: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Light Gradient Boosting Machine. This first research question is relevant to support policy making. Indeed, by identifying which factors impact the most the well-being of the elderly it would be possible to support the creation of a public health system that better supports their needs, ideally at 360 degrees. Since it would not be meaningful to give generic suggestions to the 28 European Countries taken into consideration in the Analysis, that have very different National Healthcare Systems, the Thesis will focus on the Italian National Healthcare System to provide ad-hoc policy suggestions on how the country can better support its elderly population. Therefore, the second Research Question is:

“How can Italy better support its Aging Population? And which policies can improve the quality of life of its Elderly Population?”

This would be particularly meaningful as Italy is the “oldest” country in Europe and the second “oldest” country in the world, after Japan. Indeed, based on the ISTAT population census released on the 15th December 2020 on data gathered in 2019, the average age of an Italian is 45.2 years (compared to 43 in 2011 and 31.5 in 1951) and 23,2% of its population is 65 years or older (with the remaining 63,8% being 15-64 and 13% being under 0-14). In 2019 the ratio between the population over 65 years and under 15 years is 180%, compared to 33,5% in 1951.

The “oldest” region is Liguria with an average age of its inhabitants of over 48.7 years, while the “youngest” region is Campania with an average age of 42.5 years, followed by Trentino Alto Adige, Sicilia, and Calabria (Figure 11).

Figure 11 - Average age of Italian population by region 1951 and 2019

2. Data Analysis: Methodology

Figure 12 - Data Analysis Step by Step Process

Figure 12 shows the process followed in this Thesis to analyze the data, this analysis focused on the classification of “1 - Good Aging Conditions” and “0 - Poor Aging Conditions” based on the “Healthy Aging” concept of the WHO, using both statistical and supervised machine learning models. Firstly, data were collected from easySHARE Dataset. Secondly, the data was imported in Python and Data Cleaning was performed using Pandas, being Pandas a famous Python library for data manipulation. Thirdly, the dataset was split between a Train Set and a Test Set. The Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Light Gradient Boosting Machine Models were built and trained on the Train Set. Fourthly, the Models were tested on the Test Set and adjusted based on the out-sample model performance in terms of Accuracy, Recall, Precision, and F-1 Score. Fifthly, the best model among the ones built was chosen using the criteria of Accuracy. The chosen model was then explained using SHAP values analysis.

2.1 Data Acquisition

The data was gathered from the Survey of Health, Aging and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), a research infrastructure that studies the effects of health, social, economic, and environmental policies on European citizens. SHARE is the largest pan-European social science study, providing data that allow insights in the field of public health and socio-economic living condition of European citizens.

From 2004 until today, SHARE has conducted 480.000 in-depth interviews with 140.000 people aged 50 or older living in 28 European countries and Israel. The

countries participating in the interviews are Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, and Switzerland.

SHARE is founded by the European Commission, the US National Institute on Aging, and national sources of the countries participating in the project.

SHARE is part of broad International Cooperation projects in collaboration with similar studies around the world such as HRS - Health and Retirement Study, ELSA - English Longitudinal Study of Aging, TILDA - The Irish Longitudinal Study on Aging, CHARLS - Chinese Health and Retirement Survey, ELSI-Brasil - Estudo Longitudinal de Saúde do Idoso, JSTAR - The Japanese Study of Aging and Retirement, KLoSA - The Korean Longitudinal Study of Aging, LASI - The Longitudinal Aging Study in India, and MHAS - Mexican Health and Aging Study.

Data from SHARE interviews are organized in Waves (1 to 8) that comprise data for a specific year of the interviews. Data from Wave 1 (collected in 2004-2006) to 7 (collected in 2017) are already available. SHARE Waves 3 and 7 contain also retrospective life history data. Data from Wave 8 have been collected in 2020, with a combined special COVID-19 add-on questionnaire, but are still not publicly available.

The interviews comprise 6 different research areas: Income & Wealth, Health, Health Care, Work & Retirement, Social Networks, Cognition. From these interviews, a rich database is constructed with information on health, socio-economic status, and social and family networks. Due to its richness SHARE databases are also complex: the countries participating have institutional and languages differences, combined with differentiation of data at an individual, couple, and household level.

SHARE publishes the “easySHARE” dataset, which is a simplified version of the data in its Waves for student training, and for researchers who have little experience in quantitative analyses of complex survey data. easySHARE contains the same observations as the Waves but is restricted to a subset of variables and organized as panel data. To facilitate analysis some observations are grouped in indices and recoded health, demographic, social, and economic measures allow analyses without the need of extensive data pre-processing.

In this Research we used the easySHARE version 7.1.0 released the 26th June 2020, that is based on SHARE Waves 1, 2, 3 (SHARELIFE), 4, 5, 6 and 7 (DOIs: 10.6103/SHARE.w1.710, 10.6103/SHARE.w2.710, 10.6103/SHARE.w3.710, 10.6103/SHARE.w4.710, 10.6103/SHARE.w5.710, 10.6103/SHARE.w6.710, 10.6103/SHARE.w7.710).

Therefore, in this Thesis, the data used are from Waves 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7, and cover the period from 2004 to 2017 (Figure 13).

Figure 13 - Country Wave field time overview Wave 1 - Wave 7. Retrieve from the SHARE website.

The following topics and variables are present in easySHARE:

- “1) **Demographics**: age, gender, country of birth, citizenship, education, religion, marital status, age, and gender of partner.
- 2) **Household composition**: living with partner in the same household, household size, children living in the household.
- 3) **Social support & network**: mother/father alive, number of children, residential proximity of children, number of grandchildren, number of living siblings, social activities, received and given social support.
- 4) **Childhood conditions**: number of books at age ten, relative mathematical skills at age ten, relative language skills at age ten, childhood health status, being vaccinated during childhood.
- 5) **Health and health behavior**: self-perceived health, number of chronic diseases, mental health variables, depression scale EURO-D, CASP-12 index for quality of life

and well-being, health care utilization, grip strength, body mass index, smoking and drinking behavior, vigorous activities/sports.

6) **Functional limitation indices:** mobility index, large muscle index, activities of daily living index, gross motor skills index, fine motor skills index, instrumental activities of daily living index, cognitive functions.

7) **Work & money:** current job situation, term of main job, working hours per week, satisfaction with main job, early retirement plans, able to make ends meet, imputed.” (Guide to easySHARE release 7.1.0, 2020)

2.2 Data Preparation

The easySHARE Dataset was imported in the Dataframe format using Python. The easySHARE Dataset version 7.1.0 have 365806 rows (observations) and 110 columns (variables/features).

2.2.1 Data Cleaning

The easySHARE Dataset was filtered for respondents aged 65 or older and all the observations coming from Israel were removed. Indeed, the analysis was performed on the data from the 27 Member States of the European Union (with the exclusion of the United Kingdom that left the EU on the 31st January 2020) and Switzerland. Therefore, the analysis was performed on the following 28 countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Republic of Cyprus, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland.

At this point, the Dataset had 186969 rows and 110 columns. After this operation, the Dataset was cleaned of those observations that had plus than 50% of missing values in the rows (variables). After the Data Cleaning, the Dataset had 157464 rows and 110 columns.

2.2.2 Healthy Aging Index Construction

The Healthy Aging Index (HA Index) was created based on the “Healthy Aging” WHO’s concept defined “as the process of developing and maintaining the functional ability that enables well-being in older age”. Functional Ability is made up of the **intrinsic capacity** (that in this Thesis is considered as y_1 – Ability of Daily Activities, y_2 – Physical Health, and y_3 – Mental Health), relevant **environmental characteristics**, and the **interactions between the individual and these characteristics** (that in this Thesis is considered as y_4 – Social Support and Network).

“ y - HA Index” was created as a dummy variable (0,1) defined as “1 - Good Aging Conditions” if the person has satisfactory values of y_1 - Ability of Daily Activities, y_2 - Physical Health, y_3 - Mental Health, and y_4 - Social Support and Network. If the person has not satisfactory values of even just one of y_1 , y_2 , y_3 , y_4 the HA Index is defined as “0 - Poor Aging Conditions”.

y – HA Index is a binary variable that can be described as follows:

$y = 1$ if $y_1 = 0$ and $y_2 \leq 2$ and $y_3 \geq 35$ and $y_4 =$ at least one person in his social network

$y = 0$ if $y_1 \neq 0$ and $y_2 > 2$ and $y_3 < 35$ and $y_4 \neq$ at least one person in his social network

Below a detailed description of how y_1 , y_2 , y_3 , and y_4 were constructed and how the benchmark to divide between satisfactory and unsatisfactory values for each of them was chosen based on the characteristics of the variables of the easySHARE Dataset:

- y_1 - Ability of Daily Activities: comprise the variables “adla” - Activities of daily living index (sum of the five tasks dressing, bathing or showering, eating, cutting up food, walking across a room, and getting in or out of bed) and “iadlza” - Instrumental activities of daily living index (sum of telephone calls, taking medications, managing money, shopping for groceries, and preparing a hot meal). “adla” and “iadlza” range from 0 to 5. The higher the Activities of daily living index and Instrumental activities of daily living index are, the more difficulties with these activities and the lower the mobility of the respondent. The benchmark to divide between satisfactory and unsatisfactory values of “adla” and “iadlza” was chosen as 0, that is no or very little difficulties with these basic tasks that are considered vital for the wellbeing of an elderly person. Therefore, values larger than 0 in “adla” or “iadlza” would result in an unsatisfactory value of y_1 - Ability of Daily Activities, values of “adla” and “iadlza” equal to 0 would

result in satisfactory values of y1 - Ability of Daily Activities.

- y2 - Physical Health: comprise the variable “chronic_mod” - Number of chronic diseases. The following list shows the conditions included in the index:
 - A heart attack
 - High blood pressure or hypertension
 - High blood cholesterol
 - A stroke or cerebral vascular disease
 - Diabetes or high blood sugar
 - Chronic lung disease
 - Cancer or malignant tumor
 - Stomach or duodenal ulcer, peptic ulcer
 - Parkinson disease
 - Cataracts
 - Hip fracture or femoral fracture

The benchmark to divide between satisfactory and unsatisfactory values is 2. This benchmark was chosen since for some of the above conditions there are good treatments available to reduce the impact of these conditions on the quality of life of elderly people. As an example, cataracts and hip fractures can be operated and there are cures helping with high cholesterol and diabetes. Moreover, looking at Table 1 the descriptive analysis of the index shows that 75% of the observations have 2 chronic conditions, meaning that it is quite common to have at least one of the above conditions after a certain age. Therefore, if a person has more than 2 chronic diseases, it's considered to have an unsatisfactory value of y2 - Physical Health, if a person has 2 or fewer chronic diseases, it's considered to have a satisfactory value of y2 - Physical Health.

Table 1 - Descriptive Analysis of "chronic_mod" - Number of chronic diseases

Descriptive Analysis of "chronic_mod" - Number of chronic diseases	
count	157296
mean	1.48
std	1.29
min	0
25%	0
50%	1
75%	2
max	10

- y3 - Mental Health:** comprise the variable "casp" - CASP-12 score (this score is a mental health variable included in SHARE and it is a revised version of the famous CASP -19, it measures the quality of life based on four subscales on control, autonomy, pleasure, and self-realization). The score ranges from 12 to 48 and is subsequently classified into 4 levels of quality of life with scores below 35 considered low, 35-37 moderate, 37-39 high, and scores 39-41 considered very high. The benchmark used to divide between satisfactory and unsatisfactory values is 35. Therefore, if a person has a CASP-12 score less than 35 it's considered to have an unsatisfactory value of y3 - Mental Health, if the score is greater or equals 35 it's considered to have a satisfactory value of y3 - Mental Health.

Figure 14 shows the list of questions from which the CASP-12 Score is constructed and the descriptive analysis of the "casp":

Figure 14 – CASP-12 Score Questionnaire

Here is a list of statements that people have used to describe their lives or how they feel. We would like to know how often, if at all, you think this applies to you.

(Please tick one box in each row)

	Often ₁	Sometimes ₁	Rarely ₁	Never ₁
	▼ ₁	▼ ₁	▼ ₁	▼ ₁
a) My age prevents me from doing the things I would like to	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) I feel that what happens to me is out of my control	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) I feel left out of things	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) I can do the things that I want to do	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
e) Family responsibilities prevent me from doing what I want to do	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
f) Shortage of money stops me from doing the things I want to do	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
g) I look forward to each day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
h) I feel that my life has meaning	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
i) On balance, I look back on my life with a sense of happiness	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
j) I feel full of energy these days	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
k) I feel that life is full of opportunities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
l) I feel that the future looks good for me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Source: Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe. <http://www.share-project.org/>

Table 2 - Descriptive Analysis of "casp" - CASP-12 Score

Descriptive Analysis of "casp" - CASP-12 score	
count	143400
mean	36.64
std	6.55
min	12
25%	32
50%	37
75%	42
max	48

Before using the CASP-12 as a Mental Health Variable it was used "eurod" - Depression scale EURO-D (measures the current depression as a composite index of twelve items: depressed mood, pessimism, suicidality, guilt, sleep, interest, irritability, appetite, fatigue, concentration, enjoyment and tearfulness). The scale ranges from 0 "not depressed" to 12 "very depressed". However, this variable caused poor performance in the final statistical part (probably because it's an index of current depression and does not account for the overall perception of an individual's life). Therefore, CASP-12 (that accounts for both current and past perception of life) was identified as a better and more precise score to rate the overall mental health of an individual. Interestingly, in the final Statistical Analysis "eurod" was found to be one of the main determinants of the Healthy Aging Index.

- ***y4 - Social Support and Network***: In this variable, I tried to reconstruct if the individual's social network is alive (sibling, mother, father, children, grandchildren) and the interactions among the individual and its network (received/given health outside the household, living with a partner, household size, residential proximity) inserting the variables "siblings_alive", "father_alive", "mother_alive", "partnerinhh" - Living with spouse/partner, "hhsz" - Household size, "ch001_" - Number of children, "ch021_mod" - Number of grandchildren, "ch007_hh" - At least one child in the same household, "ch007_km" - Residential proximity of children, "sp002_mod" - Received help from outside the household, "sp008_" - Given help to others outside the household. In Y4 the benchmark used are different for each variable composing Y4 based on the characteristics of each variable. The benchmark used to divide between satisfactory and

unsatisfactory values is if the person has at least one person in his social network, considering family members alive and interactions with neighbors or friends.

Therefore, if a person has not a single person in his social network it's considered to have an unsatisfactory value of y4 – Social Support and Network, if a person has at least one person in his social network it's considered to have a satisfactory value of y4 – Social Support and Network.

2.2.3 Descriptive Analysis of the Healthy Aging Index

Figure 15 plots the % of observations that have “1- Good Aging Conditions” in the HA Index over the different countries. Therefore, the HA Index is on the vertical axis of the graph while the Countries Names are represented on the horizontal axis. Just by looking at the graph is possible to see that there are significant differences among the countries.

Figure 15 - HA Index among Countries:% of "1-Good Aging Conditions"

The country that from this HA Index parameter looks to have the better quality of life in elderly age is Switzerland with 70,44% of its respondents considered to be in “Good Aging Conditions”, followed by Denmark with 61,44%, the Netherlands with 59,53%, Ireland with 59,38%, and Sweden with 58,93%. Out of the 28 countries taken into consideration for this analysis 2 countries have over 60% of its respondents considered to be in “Good Aging Conditions”, and 11 countries have over 50%.

Italy appears to be the 6th worst country in terms of aging conditions among our analysis. Indeed, in Italy only 33,42% of its respondents are considered to be in “Good Aging Conditions”. The countries performing worst than Italy are Bulgaria, Romania, Lithuania, Portugal, Greece.

Table 3 - % Respondents with "1 - Good Aging Conditions" in European Countries

Country	% of respondents with HA Index as 1
Switzerland	70,44%
Denmark	61,44%
Netherlands	59,53%
Ireland	59,38%
Sweden	58,93%
Malta	57,66%
Luxembourg	57,44%
Austria	56,27%
Finland	54,62%
Germany	53,21%
Slovenia	52,23%
Belgium	45,64%
France	43,50%
Slovakia	43,08%
Croatia	42,69%
Cyprus	42,32%
Spain	38,42%
Latvia	37,50%
Czech Rep.	36,56%
Hungary	36,15%
Poland	34,98%
Estonia	34,15%
Italy	33,42%
Bulgaria	32,29%
Romania	29,61%
Lithuania	25,97%
Portugal	23,58%
Greece	20,38%

2.3 Model Training and Testing

To verify the impact of Macroeconomic factors on the HA Index, a set of Macroeconomic country and year-specific variables retrieved from the World Data Bank was added to the easySHARE Dataset.

The variables added are GDP per capita (current US\$), Current Health Expenditure (CHE) as % Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Domestic Private Health Expenditure (PVT-D) as % Current Health Expenditure (CHE), External Health Expenditure (EXT) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE), Out-of-pocket (OOPS) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE), Domestic General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) as % Current Health Expenditure (CHE), Urban population (% of the total population), Gini index (World Bank estimate of wealth inequality), Risk of impoverishing expenditure for surgical care (% of people at risk), and Risk of catastrophic expenditure for surgical care (% of people at risk).

The components of Current Health Expenditure considered in the analysis are:

1. “Domestic Private Health Expenditure (% Of Current Health Expenditure): Share of current health expenditures funded from domestic private sources. Domestic private sources include funds from households, corporations, and non-profit organizations. Such expenditures can be either prepaid to voluntary health insurance or paid directly to healthcare providers.
2. External Health Expenditure (% Of Current Health Expenditure): Share of current health expenditures funded from external sources. External sources compose of direct foreign transfers and foreign transfers distributed by government encompassing all financial inflows into the national health system from outside the country. External sources either flow through the government scheme or are channeled through non-governmental organizations or other schemes.
3. Out-of-pocket (OOPS) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE): Share of out-of-pocket payments of total current health expenditures. Out-of-pocket payments are spending on health directly out-of-pocket by households.
4. Domestic General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) as % Current Health Expenditure (CHE). Public expenditure on health from domestic sources as a share of total public expenditure. It indicates the priority of the government

to spend on health from own domestic public resources.” (World Bank Data Catalog, 2020)

Other sources of funding of Current Health Expenditure, as Private Insurances and other Private Health Expenditures, were not considered.

The variables were added to the easySHARE Database based on the year and country of each observation.

The final dataset (composed of easySHARE plus the Macroeconomic variables) was divided between the Train Set (90% of original Dataset) and the Test Set (10% of original Dataset) with the Scikit learn function “train_test_split”, which randomly divides the observation between the two Sets. At this point, the Train Set was composed of 141717 observations and the Test Set was composed of 15747 observations. Thus with the train test split the pre-processing phase was completed.

To classify the HA Index among its values 0-1, it was used a Logistic Regression and two Ensemble algorithms based on Decisions Trees models: Random Forest and Light Gradient Boosting Machine.

Logistic Regression is one of the traditional methods to solve a binary Classification problem, or assigning to data two different classes using their features. In this case, we identified 0 as “Poor Aging Conditions” and 1 as “Good Aging Conditions”. The Logistic Regression uses the Sigmoid Distribution Function. The output is the probability from 0 to 1 of belonging in the 0 or in the 1 class.

Ensemble algorithms based on bagging and boosting, which have as building blocks the Decision Trees model were chosen because they are considered among the best methods to do predictive analysis on tabular data (as in this case) and are among the most innovative methods to analyze Social Science Phenomenon. Ensemble algorithms use the output of many decision trees, usually computing the mean or the mode of a given set of predictors, to create a stronger and less biased single predictor. Both bagging and boosting methods are used to reduce the overfitting that could arise from using a single decision tree. Indeed, in Social Science the goal is to predict, describe, and/or explain some Social phenomenon, and in this Thesis the goal is to predict if a person will have a good quality of life in its elderly age.

Decision Trees are tools that use a tree-like model to display the variables that bring to an output, it is used to help predict the course of one or more actions or show the

statistical probability that an outcome will occur. They are a powerful and widely used modeling technique to classify instances by sorting them down from the “root” (the node that performs the first split – with “nodes” being the split of a value based on a certain attribute) to the “leaves” (the terminal nodes that predict an outcome). Figure 16 graphically displays the ensembled Decision Tree of the Random Forest Model from the analysis of this Thesis.

Figure 16 - Decision Tree of the Random forest Model of this Thesis

Decision Trees have several advantages compared to more traditional methods to analyze binary data, as Logistic Regression, such as:

1. Some researchers consider Decisions Trees to be better in analyzing social science phenomenon as they “more closely mirror human decision-making” (Gareth M. James et al, 2017, p.315);
2. Trees can be displayed graphically and can be easily interpreted even by non-experts, as they are very intuitive;
3. Trees can easily handle qualitative predictors (such as age and income).

Decision Trees has one main disadvantage compared to other methods: Overfitting. Overfitting occurs when the Trees memorizes with high precision the Training Data by fitting it closely. The problem is that the model learns not only the relationships between variables in the Training data but also any noise that is present. The consequences of overfitting are:

1. Decision Trees might not always have better predictive accuracy on the Test Set than other approaches;
2. A small change in Training Data can cause a large change in the final estimated Tree.

It has been proved that by aggregating many Decisions Trees with methods such as Random Forest (Bagging Method) and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (one of the Boosting Methods) the predictive performance of the trees can be substantially improved.

Random Forest is a model made up of many Decision Trees that is based on three key concepts:

1. Random Sampling Training Data: The model creates many random samples of the Training Set (using Bootstrap technique) and creates a separate Decision Tree on each sample;
2. Random Subsets of Features for splitting nodes: The model forces the trees to split each time on a different subset of features (to avoid correlation among the trees);
3. Combining all the trees to create a single Random Forest Model, through the mode or the mean of the created set of decision trees.

Therefore, Random Forest involves creating multiple copies of the original training data set, fitting a separate decision tree to each copy by forcing the trees to split on a subset of the total number of features each time, and then combining all of the trees to create a single predictive model.

“The random forest combines hundreds or thousands of decision trees, trains each one on a slightly different set of the observations, splitting nodes in each tree considering a limited number of the features. The final predictions of the random forest are made by averaging the predictions of each individual tree.” (Will Koehrsen, 2018).

Random Forests are theoretically defined as a number of decision trees built on bootstrapped training samples (Bootstrap Sampling is an approach that simply selects random observations from the original dataset – in this case the Train Set - to obtain many different subs set from a single dataset), and each time the tree performs a split a random sample of m predictors (a subset of the total predictors p) is chosen as split candidates from the full set of p predictors. m is typically chosen to be the square root of p ($m \approx \sqrt{p}$), meaning that the number of predictors considered at each split is approximately equal to the square root of the total number of predictors. In other words, in Random Forests at each split, the algorithm is allowed to use only one of those m predictors and cannot use all the other predictors, therefore each split is forced to use different predictors.

This is helpful when the predictors are correlated among them because it forces the trees to be different one from the other and to “isolate” the impact of each predictor X_n on Y .

Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) is a Gradient Boosting Technique that is also based on Decision Trees.

Boosting works in a similar way to Random Forest, except that the trees are grown sequentially, meaning that each tree is grown using information from previously grown trees, and not independently one from another like in Random Forest. Therefore, the construction of each tree depends strongly on the trees that have already been grown. Then the Decisions Trees are combined to create a single predictive model.

A more detailed description of the boosting process is presented in the book *“Introduction to Statistical Learning”* published for the first time in 2013 by Gareth M. James, Daniela Witten, Robert Tibshirani, and Trevor Hastie. The book explains that “given the current model, we fit a decision tree to the residuals from the model. That is, we fit a tree using the current residuals, rather than the outcome Y , as the response. We then add this new decision tree into the fitted function ($f(x)$) to update the residuals. Each of these trees can be rather small, with just a few terminal nodes, determined by the parameter d in the algorithm. By fitting small trees to the residuals, we slowly improve $f(x)$ in areas where it does not perform well. The shrinkage parameter λ slows the process down even further, allowing more and different shaped trees to attack the residuals.” (Gareth M. James et al, 2017, p.321-322)

However, LightGBM is a different model compared to Random Forest and other Gradient Boosting Decision Trees Models (as the commonly known Extreme Gradient Boosting or XGBoost technique) because they split trees at a leaf-wise growth level and uses an extremely efficient gradient optimization algorithm: GBDT (the algorithm that minimizes the gradient losses of each iteration of the LightGBM).

LightGBM splits the tree at a leaf-wise growth instead of at the tree-wise growth (as most decision tree learning algorithms). This means that the algorithm splits in order to minimize the leaf loss, and therefore chooses the leaf with max delta loss to grow. Below is a graphical representation of the leaf-wise tree growth.

Leaf-wise splitting may cause over-fitting when the dataset is small, in order to avoid this LightGBM includes the “max_depth” parameter to limit tree depth. However, this was not the case for this Thesis as the easySHARE dataset is quite big.

After having trained the Logistic Regression, Random forest, and Light Gradient Boosting Machine model on the training data, the model performance is evaluated on the Test data.

3. Data Analysis: Findings

To evaluate the performance of Classification Models on the Test Set (data for which the true values are known) usually a Confusion Matrix is used to display:

- True Positive (TP): the correctly predicted positive values, in other words, the number of observations where the actual value is 1 and corresponds to the predicted value which is also 1;
- True Negative (TN): the correctly predicted negative values, in other words, the number of observations where the actual value is 0 and corresponds to the predicted value which is also 0;
- False Positive (FP) – Type I Error: When the actual value is 0 and the predicted value is 1;
- False Negative (FN) – Type II Error: When the actual value is 1 but the predicted value is 0.

		Predicted	
		Negative	Positive
Actual	Negative	True Negative	False Positive
	Positive	False Negative	True Positive

The key metrics to evaluate a Classification Problem are:

- **Accuracy:** that is the number of correct predictions made by the model divided by the total number of predictions. Accuracy is very useful when target classes are well balanced, meaning that values of false positive and false negatives are almost the same (as in the case of this Thesis).

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{True Positive} + \text{True Negative}}{(\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive} + \text{True Negative} + \text{False Negative})}$$

- **Recall:** that is the number of true positives divided by the number of true positives plus the number of false negatives.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{(\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative})}$$

- **Precision:** that the number of true positives divided by the number of true positives plus the number of false positives. In other words, it is the ability of a classification model to identify only the relevant data points.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{(\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive})}$$

While Recall expresses the ability to find all relevant instances in a dataset, Precision expresses the proportion of the data points our model says were relevant actually were relevant. For this reason, often there is a trade-off between Recall and Precision. To find an optimal blend of Precision and Recall the two metrics are combined in the F1 score.

- **F1-Score:** that is the harmonic mean of precision and recall taking both metrics into account. By using harmonic mean instead of simple average extreme values are punished.

$$F_1 = 2 * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}}$$

Therefore, Accuracy is one of the most indicated metrics to evaluate model performances in case of false positives and false negatives having a similar cost and if the classes are well distributed. While F1-Score is a more precise metric if the classes are unevenly distributed and if the cost of false positives and false negatives are very different.

In this Thesis, the classes are well distributed (86127 observations with “0 – Poor Aging Conditions”, and 71337 observations with “1 - Good Aging Conditions”) and the cost of false positive and false negative is not very different. Indeed, on one side false positives are the errors that predict “1- Good Aging Conditions” while the actual value is “0 – Poor Aging Conditions”, on the other side false negatives are the errors that predict “0 – Poor Aging Conditions” while the actual value is “1 - Good Aging Conditions”. Based on the research Question with the aim of identifying which features impact the HA Index and in which directions the cost of these two types of errors is similar as in both cases they create noise, in different directions, on the final impact of a feature on the HA Index of individuals. To try to counterbalance the two opposite effects, the balance of the model in terms of Type I and Type II errors will be also considered as a metric. Therefore, Accuracy and balance will be used as the main indicators to evaluate the performance of the different Classification Methods used.

3.1 Logistic Regression

Figure 17 - Logistic Regression Confusion Matrix

In the Logistic Regression the Confusion Matrix shows:

- True Positive (TP): 0.72
- True Negative (TN): 0.75
- False Positive (FP) – Type I Error: 0.25
- False Negative (FN) – Type II Error: 0.28

Table 4 - Logistic Regression Classification Report

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0.0	0.76	0.75	0.76	8599
1.0	0.70	0.72	0.71	7148
Accuracy			0.74	15747
Macro Avg	0.73	0.74	0.73	15747
Weighted Avg	0.74	0.74	0.74	15747

3.2 Random Forest

Figure 18 - Random Forest Confusion Matrix

In the Random Forest the Confusion Matrix shows:

- True Positive (TP): 0.76
- True Negative (TN): 0.77
- False Positive (FP) – Type I Error: 0.23
- False Negative (FN) – Type II Error: 0.24

Table 5 - Random Forest Classification Report

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0.0	0.79	0.77	0.78	8599
1.0	0.73	0.76	0.75	7148
Accuracy			0.77	15747
Macro Avg	0.76	0.76	0.76	15747
Weighted Avg	0.77	0.77	0.77	15747

3.3 Light Gradient Boosting Machine

Figure 19 - LightGBM Confusion Matrix

In the Light Gradient Boosting Machine the Confusion Matrix shows:

- True Positive (TP): 0.77
- True Negative (TN): 0.77
- False Positive (FP) – Type I Error: 0.23
- False Negative (FN) – Type II Error: 0.23

Table 6 - LightGBM Classification Report

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0.0	0.80	0.77	0.79	8599
1.0	0.74	0.77	0.76	7148
Accuracy			0.77	15747
Macro Avg	0.77	0.77	0.77	15747
Weighted Avg	0.77	0.77	0.77	15747

All the models used performed well with an accuracy of respectively 74% for Logistic Regression, 77% for Random Forest, and 77% for Light Gradient Boosting Machine. The Light Gradient Boosting Machine performed slightly better than Random Forest because the former is a very balanced model with both Type I and Type II errors at 0,23.

Considering the fact that the model tries to predict the quality of life in elderly age that is something very subjective being related to human nature, an accuracy of 77% for Light Gradient Boosting Machine can be considered a reliable result. Indeed, Social Science phenomenon are hard to predict because they are subject to bias and can be impacted by a multitude of factors that cannot be easily included in data analysis, also with machine learning techniques.

Therefore, Light Gradient Boosting Machine results are analyzed in detail below and its findings will be used to develop and design the Policy Insights for Italy.

3.4 SHAP Value for Light Gradient Boosting Machine Results Interpretation

Machine Learning Models are often referred to as “black boxes”, because they usually make accurate predictions but their results are hard to interpret because of the multitude of computations performed. To interpret the results it has been used one of the most popular libraries for Machine Learning interpretability: the SHAP library. The library uses Shapley values that are a concept derived from Game Theory introduced by Lloyd Shapley in 1951 that won the Nobel Prize in Economics in 2012.

Game theory is the process of modeling the strategic interactions between players in a situation where two or more players (or factors) work to achieve the desired outcome. The Shapley value ensures each player gets assigned the share of the final outcome it has generated with this work. The Shapley values are very useful in situations where the contribution of the different players is unequal, but all the players have worked together in cooperation to obtain the final result.

The Shapley values consider each feature (in this case: X_n) as a player and the prediction (in this case: y - HA Index) as the final reward, its outcome tells how it would be fair to distribute the final reward among the players. In other words, Shapley values identify the marginal contribution of each independent variable towards the final outcome.

Figure 20 shows the LightGBM features of the dataset on the y axis and the impact they have on the final model output (the y - HA Index) on the x-axis.

The values on the x-axis that are on the left side (from 0 “SHAP Value”) are the ones that impact negatively the final outcome of the dependent variables, therefore moving it towards the “0 – Poor Aging Conditions”. Instead, the values on the x-axis that are on the right side (from 0 “SHAP Value”) are the ones that impact positively the final outcome of the dependent variables, therefore moving it towards the 1 – Good Aging Conditions. The scale of colors instead signals whether it is a high or a low value of the independent variable that is moving the dependent variable in a certain direction. Below there is a detailed description of how each independent variable is impacting the HA Index.

Figure 20 - SHAP Value Summary Plot with LightGBM

SHAP Value Summary Plot combines the feature importance (the descending order of the independent variables impacting y) with the feature effects (the direction of the impact of the independent variables) and therefore provides an overview of the model. Each dot represents an observation of the dataset.

The main variables impacting HA, ranked in descending order for feature importance, are presented in Table 7.

Table 7 - SHAP Value Main Impacting Features with LightGBM

Independent Variable Name	Independent Variable Description ¹	High Values Impact	Low Values Impact
“grossmotor” - Gross Motor Skills Index	Comprises walking 100 meters, walking across a room, climbing one flight of stairs, and bathing or showering. The higher the index is the more difficulties with the activities and the lower the gross motor skills of the respondent. “grossmotor” ranges from 0 to 4.	Negative Impact	Positive Impact
“finemotor” - Fine Motor Skills Index	Comprises picking up a small coin, eating/cutting up food, and dressing. The higher the index is the more difficulties with the above activities and the lower the fine motor skills of the respondent. “finemotor” ranges from 0 to 3.	Negative Impact	Positive Impact
“sphus” - Self-perceived health	The higher the index is the poorer the self-perceived health is and the lower the better the self-perceived health of the respondent is. “sphus” ranges from 1 to 5.	Negative Impact	Positive Impact
“eurod” - Depression scale EURO-D	The EURO-D symptom scale measures the current depression and is a composite	Negative Impact	Positive Impact

¹ All the Variables Description are from easySHARE Guide release 7.1.0 and from World Bank Data Catalog.

	<p>index of twelve items: depressed mood, pessimism, suicidality, guilt, sleep, interest, irritability, appetite, fatigue, concentration, enjoyment, and tearfulness. The scale ranges from 0 “not depressed” to 12 “very depressed”.</p>		
<p>“lgmuscle” - Large Muscle Index</p>	<p>Comprises sitting two hours, getting up from a chair, stooping, kneeling, crouching, and pulling or pushing large objects. The higher the index, the more difficulties with the activities and the lower the mobility of the respondent. “lgmuscle” ranges from 0 to 4.</p>	<p>Negative Impact</p>	<p>Positive Impact</p>
<p>“co007” - Household able to make ends meet</p>	<p>The question is: “Thinking of your household’s total monthly income, would you say that your household is able to make ends meet...”. The higher the index, the more easily the household is able to make ends meet, the lower the more difficult it is. “co007” ranges from 1 to 4.</p>	<p>Positive Impact</p>	<p>Negative Impact</p>
<p>“GDP per capita”</p>	<p>GDP per capita of the country.</p>	<p>Positive Impact</p>	<p>Negative Impact</p>

“recall_1” - Recall of words (a memory score)	Contains the number of words recalled in the first trial of the word recall task. It ranges from 0 to 10.	Positive Impact	Negative Impact
“hc002_mod” - Number of doctor visits within the past year	The question behind this variable is: “During the last twelve months, about how many times in total have you seen or talked to a medical doctor about your health?”.	Negative Impact	Positive Impact
“female” – Gender of the respondent	“dummy”- style coded gender variable. 0: male; 1: female.	Positive Impact	Negative Impact
“maxgrip” - Maximum of grip strength measure (a measure of physical strength)	The variable maxgrip is defined as the maximum grip strength measurement of both hands or of one hand.	Positive Impact	Negative Impact
“br015_” – Frequency of Vigorous activities	Information on the frequency of doing vigorous activities such as sports, heavy housework, or a job that involves physical labor. The higher the index, the less often these activities are done, the lower the more often these activities are done. “br015_” ranges from 1 to 4.	Positive Impact	Negative Impact

<p>“gghed_che” - Domestic General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) as % Current Health Expenditure (CHE)</p>	<p>“Public expenditure on health from domestic sources as a share of total public expenditure. It indicates the priority of the government to spend on health from own domestic public resources.” (World Bank Data Catalog, 2020)</p>	<p>Mixed Effects</p>	<p>Mixed Effects</p>
<p>“thinc_m” - Household net income</p>	<p>The household net income is a measure of the total disposable income of a household, calculated as the sum of the disposable income of its components.</p>	<p>Positive Impact</p>	<p>Negative Impact</p>
<p>“oops_che” - Out-of-pocket (OOPS) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)</p>	<p>“Share of out-of-pocket payments of total current health expenditures. Out-of-pocket payments are spending on health directly out-of-pocket by households.” (World Bank Data Catalog, 2021)</p>	<p>Negative Impact</p>	<p>Mixed Effects</p>
<p>“Urban population (% of the total population)”</p>	<p>“Urban population refers to people living in urban areas as defined by national statistical offices. The data are collected and smoothed by United</p>	<p>Negative Impact</p>	<p>Positive Impact</p>

	Nations Population Division.” (World Bank Data Catalog, 2020)		
“che_gdp” - Current Health Expenditure (CHE) as % Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	“Level of current health expenditure expressed as a percentage of GDP. Estimates of current health expenditures include healthcare goods and services consumed during each year. This indicator does not include capital health expenditures such as buildings, machinery, IT and stocks of vaccines for emergency or outbreaks.” (World Bank Data Catalog, 2020)	Mixed Effects	Negative Impact
“Gini Index” - (World Bank estimate)	The measure of income inequality or wealth inequality within a nation. The higher the Index is the more inequality there is in the country. The Gini Index ranges from 0 to 1, with 0 corresponding to pure equidistribution and 1 corresponding to the situation where one person receives all the income of the country while all the others have zero income. Most European nations usually have Gini coefficients between 0.24 and 0.36.	Negative Impact	Positive Impact

"bmi" - Body Mass Index	This variable is based on individual weight and height. It is calculated according to the formula: $BMI = \frac{weight}{(height * height) * 10\ 000}$.	Negative Impact	Positive Impact
"eduyears_mod" - Years of education	Overall years of education that an individual had in their life	Positive Impact	Negative Impact

Most of the independent variables have a clear separation between the blue and the red dots (as "grossmotor", "finemotor", "sphus", "eurod", etc.), meaning that there is a clear separation between the impact of high values and low values. Other variables as "gghed_che", "oops_che", and "che_gdp" have blue and red dots partially overlapping each other and with mixing directions. This suggests that sometimes increasing that feature leads to higher predictions, and other times it leads to a lower prediction. In other words, both high and low values of the feature can have both positive and negative effects on the predicted y. These "Mixed Effects" are usually caused by interactions with other variables.

To investigate the interaction between these variables it was used the SHAP Dependence Contribution Plots. Among the different Plots analyzed it was possible to conclude that "gghed_che" - Domestic General Government Health Expenditure and "oops_che" - Out-of-pocket Expenditure interacts with each other. In the SHAP Dependence Contribution Plots the horizontal location is the actual value of a feature from the dataset (in this case "gghed_che"), the colors represent the actual value of another feature from the dataset (in this case "oops_che") and the vertical location shows what having that value did to the prediction.

Figure 21 - SHAP Dependence Contribution Plot "gghed_che" and "oops_che"

Figure 21 shows how high values of “gghed_che” are usually associated with low values of “oops_che”, while lower values of “gghed_che” are usually associated with higher values of “oops_che”. Very low values of “gghed_che” (around 30%) associated with high values of “oops_che” (between 25% and 30+%) impact the prediction of the HA Index in different directions, this probably depends on national differences on how the National Healthcare Services and its expenditures are organized. The rest of the graph is similar to a pretty flat curve that curves down at around 65% of “gghed_che” and 10% to 20% of “oops_che” (meaning that of the Current Health Expenditure 65% is covered by Domestic General Government Health Expenditure and 10% to 20% is covered by Out-of-pocket Expenditure). Therefore, growing values of “gghed_che” and declining values of “oops_che” are associated with a positive impact on HA Index until around respectively 65% and 10% to 20%, and then the positive impact gradually declines becoming negative.

This means that increasing the Domestic General Government Health Expenditure when the Out-of-pocket Expenditure is high has a positive impact on the HA Index, by gradually reducing the Out-of-pocket Expenditure. However, after the Domestic General Government Health Expenditure reaches 65% of the Current Health Expenditure and the Out-of-pocket Expenditure reaches low values (10% or 20% of Current Health Expenditure) the positive impact of rising the Domestic General Government Health Expenditure gradually declines becoming negative.

4. Policy Insights for Italy's Elderly Support

The phenomenon of Aging Population constitutes one of the major challenges of public systems across Europe, including Italy. The development of an integrated Policy by the public sector that coordinates the priorities according to the needs of the older population is an important challenge of the next years. This chapter of the Thesis will focus on the Italian situation, by assessing the current Long Term Care Services in the country and proposing Policy Suggestions to improve the quality of life of the older population in Italy, based on the variables impacting the Healthy Aging Index (Healthy Aging definition of WHO) in the Light Gradient Boosting Machine model.

4.1 An Overview of the Italian Long Term Care Services

The Italian Public Healthcare and Social Services for the elderly are mainly covered by the Long Term Care (LTC) Services, which is historically characterized for large levels of complexity and fragmentation caused by mainly two reasons: firstly, the LTC Services were not born from a defined and organized model, as it was the case for the National Healthcare System (SSN) introduced in 1978, but it is the result of subsequent legislative interventions (Rotolo, 2014); secondly, it is characterized by a strong fragmentation in the allocation of skills and resources among many actors at different levels of government.

The interventions offered by the Italian LTC system can be divided into two macro-categories:

- **Cash Transfers:** These are direct monetary contributions to the user, among which the most important is the Accompaniment Allowance (IDA), provided by the National Social Security Institute (INPS) both to the elderly over 65 who are not self-sufficient and to invalids under the age of 65. The amount of the transfer is fixed and equal to approximately € 515 per month. Additionally to IDA, the municipalities (and in some cases also the Regions and the local health authorities) can issue the so-called "nursing checks" or "vouchers" to support assistance and care at home for not self-sufficient people.
- **Actual Services:** There are 3 categories of services for the not self-sufficient elderly, which in most cases are compatible with the receipt of financial contributions: Domiciliary/Home, Semi-residential, and Residential services.

Domiciliary/Home services are Integrated Home Care (ADI) – organized by the Local Health Authorities (ASLs) and municipalities – that allows people not self-sufficient to be cared for by nurses or other health personnel at home, shortening or avoiding hospitalization, and Home Assistance Service (SAD or AD) – organized by municipalities – that is a service characterized by greater social support. Semi-residential services are provided in structures operating only during the day (i.e. Day Centers) that support the elderly that are usually in conditions of partial self-sufficiency or cognitive decay. Residential services are structures with “hotel” characteristics that host temporarily or permanently the not self-sufficient person, they are called differently based on the Region (i.e. RSA, Nursing homes, etc.) and can offer a variety of different services (apartment groups, sheltered residences, etc.).

The companies that offer LTC services are of 2 different profiles: small players that usually offer just one service and 18 big players that try to offer vertically integrated services (6 cooperatives, 4 public companies for peoples’ services (ASP), 4 private groups, and 4 foundations - all of ecclesiastical derivation or connotation). The majority operates in Northern Italy, some operate in Central Italy, three are also present in the South, while only one currently operates in the Islands. This data is consistent with the fact that services for the elderly are less widespread in Central and Southern Italy based on ISTAT analysis.

From the data on the 18 major players in the LTC sector, the consolidation of new services combined with the “traditional” supply chain seems to emerge, proposing more settings for taking care of families and elderly users in an attempt to accompany the evolution of needs through the possibility of accessing different services with different assistance intentions based on the evolving condition of the elderly. To complement these, various providers are also equipping themselves for a wider range of family needs, including the theme of accompaniment and psychological support.

The majority of the players (15) combine the offer of the traditional Residential services with Semi-residential (daytime) and Home services, thus composing the complete Social-Health chain on the three most typical settings present in all regional contexts. Eight players also manage Social-Residential services for the elderly, which are residential services without any Health Care service but only with Social services. These are apartment groups, residences, mini-lodgings, and other ways of living that

include forms of aggregation and related assistance services, but only in the context of socializing and daily life. These types of Residential services are mainly paid by families. A few players (4) also offer health-related, services such as rehabilitation services (both outpatient and residential) or outpatient services of various kinds. Moreover, other players (12 in total) offer front office family services for a fee and counseling services. Front offices are information services to guide and support families in accessing and attending services, while counseling is operational or psychological counseling services for families, always in support of the management of not self-sufficiency.

The 18 big players are mainly focused on services financed by public funds. In 2019, based on CERGAS SDA Bocconi analysis, 84% of the big players' income by socio-health activities was from accredited services or public agreements and only 16% from private market services.

4.2 LTC Services Coverage Rate and Private Caregiving

Currently the Italian LTC system assists just over 50% of not self-sufficient elderly people in Italy and in most cases offer insufficient services. Indeed, in 2016 with 2.9 million estimated not self-sufficient individuals in Italy only 1.5 million (equal to 52%) of elderly people in LTC benefited from the Accompaniment Allowance (IDA) and one or more Actual services. These numbers are significantly lower than in other countries. For example, in Germany - where epidemiological and aging trends are similar to Italy - 2.8 million elderly people receive public LTC services (Cinelli and Longo, 2021).

The elderly who benefits from the IDA often also benefit from one or more Actual services. In particular, 287 thousand elderly people benefit from Residential services, 294 thousand elderly people benefit from Semi-residential services, and 911 thousand elderly people receive Home services (ADI and SAD). According to a study by CERGAS SDA Bocconi, on average the hours of ADI per elderly person assisted were equal to 16 hours per year in 2016. Meaning that this service is limited to ensuring the transition from one care setting to another (mainly supporting the recovery of patients out of the hospital) but it is not a stable path of social and health care. Therefore, the main LTC Actual Services for the elderly are IDA, Semi-residential, and Residential Services (Cinelli and Longo, 2021).

Actual Services can be furtherly divided between Social-Health Care services – comprising Residential services (such as sheltered residences and nursing homes or rehabilitation for the elderly - RSA), Semi-residential, and Home Care (ADI) - and Social Services – comprising Residential services that reproduce or facilitate the typical living conditions of a family context (housing community, family-type communities, apartment groups, housing brokerage and/or allocation of accommodation, reception of the elderly in families), Semi-residential services for the promotion and coordination of playful and recreational activities, social, educational, cultural, sporting and for socialization, and Home assistance services organized by the municipalities (SAD). In 2016 1.1 million individuals were under Socio-Health Care services - 36,97% of the total LTC coverage - and just 400 thousand were under Social Services - 14,28% of the total LTC coverage (Fosti and Notarnicola, 2020).

Figure 22 shows the coverage trend of Socio-Health Care services over the years 2013-2016, although the total coverage is increasing over the years, alongside a growth of the share of the population that need these services, this is driven by the increase in coverage through ADI, that as previously discussed is currently not a stable path of social and health care for the elderly with just 16 hours per elderly per year.

Figure 22 - Coverage Rate of Italian Public LTC Actual Services in the years 2013-2016.

Retrieved from: CERGAS SDA Bocconi - 3° Rapporto Osservatorio Long Term Care (2020).

Considering the lack of coverage of the Italian LTC System and in absence of other care solutions, families have devised a do-it-yourself solution to support the elderly. Private caregiving covers the rest of the population in need that is not assisted by the Public LTC System. It is based on the support of the elderly from family members and paid caregivers (usually foreigner women between 45 and 55 years old that assist and supervise the elderly in their daily life) that lead to the birth of one of the largest and most relevant sectors in our country the “caregiver” market. In 2019 it was estimated

by CERGAS SDA Bocconi that more than 1 million caregivers were present in Italy, based on the Pasquinelli e Rusmini methodology, and that more than 600 thousand of these were operating on the irregular market (60% of the total). The wide proportion of the irregular market can be explained by the difference in terms of cost between hiring regularly or irregularly a caregiver, in the former case the yearly cost is estimated at 17.000€ while in the latter at around 10.000€ - however no official estimates are available.

Figure 23 shows that caregivers are more present in Northern regions, despite being the territories in which Public LTC Services for taking care of the not self-sufficient are more widespread, but they are also very present in the Central regions (especially in Lazio) and in Sardegna, which in the context of Southern Italy and the Islands is configured as an outlier.

Figure 23 - Number of caregivers in Italian regions and incidence every 100 over75 not self-sufficient inhabitants in the year 2018.

Retrieved from: CERGAS SDA Bocconi - 2° Rapporto Osservatorio Long Term Care (2019).

An ISTAT report recalls that in 2018 there were 2,827,000 people aged 18-64 in Italy that cared for sick, disabled, or elderly family members and that more than a third of people in the same age group had tasks and responsibilities for coordinating the care of a family member. The data also confirm for 2018 that these are mainly women for whom this condition has impacted job choices. In Italy even more markedly than in other EU28 countries, women have changed their choice to enter the world of work or their activity based on the need to care for the elderly: for example, over 50% had to

be absent for over a month during a working year to care duties and 39% continuously request permits for the same reason.

4.3 Policy Insights for the Italian LTC System

The main variables impacting the Healthy Aging Index in the Light Gradient Boosting Machine Model (analyzed in Chapter 3.4 with the SHAP values) can be divided into clusters of actions that the Government can have an impact on:

- **LTC Actual Services:** During the analysis have been identified variables that can be impacted by the LTC Actual Services interventions of the Government, aimed at supporting Physical and Mental Health of elderly individuals, both with Prevention Services, aimed at preventing the deterioration of Physical and Mental Health conditions in individuals that are still self-sufficient, and with Support Services, aimed at supporting the Physical and Mental Health conditions in individuals that are not anymore self-sufficient and whose decay is irreversible. These variables are: “grossmotor” - Gross Motor Skills Index, “finemotor” - Fine Motor Skills Index, “eurod” - Depression scale EURO-D, “lgmuscle” - Large Muscle Index, “recall_1” - Recall of words (a memory score), “hc002_mod” - Number of doctor visits within the past year “maxgrip” - Maximum of grip strength measure (a measure of physical strength), “br015_” – Frequency of Vigorous activities, “Urban population (% of the total population)”, “bmi” - Body Mass Index. Chapter 4.3.1 proposes a focus on the interventions that the Government can adopt in this field.
- **LTC Cash Transfers:** During the analysis have been identified variables that can be impacted by the LTC Cash Transfers interventions of the Government, aimed at supporting elderly individuals financially. These variables are: “co007” - Household able to make ends meet, “gghed_che” - Domestic General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) as % Current Health Expenditure (CHE), “thinc_m” - Household net income, “oops_che” - Out-of-pocket (OOPS) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE). Chapter 4.3.2 proposes a focus on the interventions that the Government can adopt in this field.
- **Social and Economic Policies:** During the analysis have been identified variables that can be impacted by Social Policies of the Government (“Gini

Index” - World Bank estimate, and “edueyears_mod” - Years of education) and Economic Policies (“GDP per capita”, and “che_gdp” - Current Health Expenditure (CHE) as % Gross Domestic Product (GDP). These variables can be impacted by Policies that aim to economically develop the society and grant equal conditions and access to possibilities for the individuals. Social and Economic Policies usually are long-term and very complex interventions that need several years to be implemented and to see the first results, therefore the interventions will not be covered in this Thesis.

- **Out of Government Scope:** During the analysis have been identified variables that are out of the area of impact of the Government’s policies. These variables are: “sphus” - Self-perceived health, “female” – Gender of the respondent. These variables cannot be impacted by the actions of the Government and will be therefore excluded from the considerations covered in the next chapters.

The Policy suggestions proposed in this Thesis, based on the Light Gradient Boosting Machine results, to improve Italy’s elderly support are summarized in Table 8.

The adoption of these Policies would improve the Healthy Aging Index in Italy and are based on the current Long Term Care Services in Italy. The proposed Policies address different variables impacting the Healthy Aging index and shall be addressed not as individual suggestions but as an integrated proposal of Policies interconnected with each other that positively impact, directly or indirectly, the living conditions of the elderly in Italy.

Table 8 - Proposed Policy Suggestions for Italy to improve Healthy Aging

LTC Macro-category	Policy Suggestion	Impacted Healthy Aging Variables
Actual Services	1. Invest in MicroServices and Technology to support Physical and Mental Health	<p><u>Physical Health</u>: “grossmotor” - Gross Motor Skills Index, “finemotor” - Fine Motor Skills Index, “lgmuscle” - Large Muscle Index, “maxgrip” - Maximum of grip strength measure (a measure of physical strength), and “bmi” - Body Mass Index.</p> <p><u>Mental Health</u>: “eurod” - Depression scale EURO-D, and “recall_1” - Recall of words (a memory score).</p>
	2. Reorganize the Public LTC Network: Integrate Private and Non-profit offering and Create a Unified Information System	“hc002_mod” - Number of doctor visits within the past year, and “br015_” - Frequency of Vigorous activities.
	3. Adequate Urban and Housing settings	“Urban population (% of the total population)”.
Cash Transfers	1. Reorganization of Cash Resources and Allocation Criteria	“co007” - Household able to make ends meet and “thinc_m” - Household net income.
	2. Out of Pocket Upgrading of Public LTC Services	"gghed_che" - Domestic general government health expenditure and "oops_che" - Out-of-pocket expenditure.
	3. Promote Private LTC Insurance	

4.3.1 Actual Services

In this Chapter are proposed 3 initiatives to widen the LTC offering (and therefore increase the audience of users and the coverage rate of the Public Network) and better respond to families' preferences and elderly needs. The suggestion shall impact positively the Physical Health variables “grossmotor” - Gross Motor Skills Index, “finemotor” - Fine Motor Skills Index, “lgmuscle” - Large Muscle Index, “maxgrip” - Maximum of grip strength measure (a measure of physical strength), and “bmi” - Body Mass Index, the Mental Health variables “recall_1” - Recall of words (a memory score), and “eurod” - Depression scale EURO-D, and “hc002_mod” - Number of doctor visits within the past year, “br015_” - Frequency of Vigorous activities, and “Urban population (% of the total population)”.

1. Invest in MicroServices and Technology to support Physical and Mental Health

Being in good Physical and Mental Health is a condition *sine qua non* Healthy Aging is not possible. The SHAP values analysis highlights that several physical mobility and strength body measures are among the main determinants of Healthy Aging: “grossmotor” - Gross Motor Skills Index, “finemotor” - Fine Motor Skills Index, “lgmuscle” - Large Muscle Index, “maxgrip” - Maximum of grip strength measure (a measure of physical strength), and “bmi” - Body Mass Index. Moreover, the SHAP values analysis highlights the correlation between Mental Health and the Healthy Aging Index with the variables “eurod” - Depression scale EURO-D, and “recall_1” - Recall of words (a memory score).

Physical and Mental Health is something that naturally gradually declines with time, or it can sharply decrease due to shocking happenings as physical trauma or an illness (being it physical or mental).

Social Services currently cover just 14,28% of the LTC coverage but considering the impact of physical and mental health in the Healthy Aging Index it would be advisable to widen the offering of prevention services when the individual is still partially self-sufficient, with partnerships with Private and Non Profit Organizations. The Government needs to increase its offering of Social Microservices to support the prevention of natural physical and mental decay by keeping the elderly in an active status. This is one of those areas in which the Government has to pursue a

“complementary” integration between Public and Private services for the elderly to covers all the needs of the elderly at 360°.

A possible solution would be giving the possibility to elderly to be enrolled in gentle sports courses and in cultural, educational, social, and recreational activities to support their psychological and mental well-being in Private and Non- Profit affiliated structures at reduced prices or by providing *ad-hoc* “vouchers” to purchase this kind of services.

Another solution is to use technology and digital tools to support and promote prevention, disease monitoring, and health management lifestyle. The Government could partner with digital companies producing devices and applications for Physical and Mental health to increase the adoption of these tools through tiered prices or “vouchers” and financing *ad-hoc* tools for their needs. By doing this, many elderly could better monitor their health status and change their habits to prevent physical and mental decay through:

- *Devices and Fitness Application for Physical Health Monitoring*: Technology can increase awareness and knowledge of the elderly on their state of physical health through wearables devices, thus allowing them to manage and change their habits. A classic example is the step counter can allow the elderly to keep track of how much they walked during the day. Other possibilities include financing the design of smartphones or computer fitness applications tailored to the needs of the elderly that guide them with at-home on gentle exercises to keep active and delay physical decay.
- *Communication and Games for Mental Health Support*: Technology can support in creating and maintaining connections and interactions with other people. This is especially meaningful to provide help to the caregiver in the management of the elderly person (with the function of monitoring and communicating the elderly in their setting that, in most cases, it is the home of the elderly or the family). This could be meaningful to support the participation of family members in the daily life of the elderly, even if they are not physically there, by positively impacting the “eurod” - Depression scale EURO-D that highlighted in the analysis that many elderly are affected by depression. Moreover, it would be advisable to use technology to develop activities to support “recall_1” - Recall of words (a memory score), such as memory or decision-making virtual reality games to keep active the mind of the elderly with a daily exercise.

2. Reorganize the Public LTC Network: Integrate Private and Non-profit offering and Create a Unified Information System

Families organize the assistance for the elderly by recomposing information, resources, and services to manage the continuity of care between different private and public settings with different Social and Health Care offerings. Families and/or elderly prefer to keep their home as the place of treatment and recurring to hospital treatment when the elderly need more professional support. OASI Report of 2016, 2017, and 2018 highlights how in 2015 the data shows that 68% of elderly had done one hospitalization, while in 32% of cases (680,731 elderly) had more than one hospitalization (at least two), for an average of 2.6 hospitalizations per person. Moreover, 57% of hospitalizations take place at the request of the families (probably through access to the emergency room) and 90% of hospitalizations end with a home discharge.

This is coherent with the results obtained in this analysis for the variable “hc002_mod” - Number of doctor visits within the past year. Indeed, the SHAP analysis shows that a high number of doctor visits in a year has a negative impact on the Healthy Aging Index. This figure is normal as going on with the years the need of medical care improves, but it also means that continuous doctor visits are not providing the right treatments, being not coherent with the elderly needs, and therefore not helping the individual in improving his quality of life. An analysis of CERGAS SDA Bocconi on the reasons that tend families to exclude Residential Services are: Service is too expensive (48%), Elderly refusal (28%), Lack of consistency with the elderly's care needs (23%), Absence of seats/waiting list too long (19%), Family disagreement with respect to the choice of the structure (8%), and Geographical distance of the property from home (5%).

Only when care at home becomes unsustainable, they consider the possibility of Residential Services. This shows that families identify the RSA as a place of the last instance for the management of complex cases and perceive it as the only valid alternative to care at home.

Families do not perceive a sense of continuity of care in the LTC system, are not aware of the network of LTC offerings, and see hospital and doctor visits as the only response for the lack of LTC response. This brings to light the need to: 1) Integrate Private and Non-profit offerings into the Public Network, and 2) Organize Public Counselling and a

Regional Information System to offer guidance to families among the LTC offering and identify the service more suited to the elderly's conditions.

I. Integrate Public Network with Private and Non-profit Offering

The SHAP analysis of “br015_” – Frequency of Vigorous activities shows that the elderly that perform doing vigorous activities, such as heavy housework or a job that involves physical labor have the worst Healthy Aging. This means that there are elderly that are still completely or partially self-sufficient that would require some help for household work (offered by Home care LTC services) but are not receiving it. The expenditure for Residential services is equal to € 3.7 billion, mainly incurred for health services, while the resources used to finance Home and Semi-residential services amount respectively to € 1.9 billion and € 0.9 billion. With these funds, the Home services cover only 31% - 911 thousand people - of the not self-sufficient in Italy while the Semi-residential services cover only the 10% - 294 thousand people (Cinelli and Longo, 2021). These figures associated with the fact that ADI covered 16 hours of service per elderly per year in 2016 show how the offering is not commensurate with the demand.

To make up for this lack in the LTC system families often recur to paid caregivers, fueling one of the largest irregular markets in Italy. A possible solution is to activate in each Region a network of Public, Private, and Non-profit providers with regulated tariffs in which families and not self-sufficient people with IDA can freely choose the provider, negotiating directly the portfolio of services they intend to receive. This would gradually make it possible to create a professional market for assistance services. Some regions (among the last Lombardia and Emilia Romagna) have tried to put forward initiatives to integrate the private sector of paid caregivers in the Public network (also to reduce the proportion of its irregular market) with two initiatives:

- 1) Creating a Register of paid caregivers, to act on the professionalism and training of the workers to ensure some form of quality and safety of the service;
- 2) The introduction of vouchers, deductions, checks, or other methods to support the regularization of paid caregivers (Fosti and Notarnicola, 2018).

Another possibility is supporting various Non-profit initiatives to keep the elderly in their community, also through the training of non-specialized caregivers and the use of communitarian systems as the Bank of Time (Fattore, 2020).

II. Reorganize LTC Information System: Counselling and Regional Information Systems

According to an analysis of CERGAS SDA Bocconi out of 342 surveys 69% of respondents stated to have never received guidance or support services for finding the service most suited to the needs of the elderly, and only 24% have received some kind of support from public services with the remaining 7% receiving support from private services (often for a fee). The scenario confirms the fragmented approach of the LTC which does not have a reference actor capable of directing individual paths.

The different programs of the current LTC system have different and not integrated information systems. Data and information on services for not self-sufficient elderly are fragmented among the information systems of INPS for the Accompaniment Indemnity (IDA), of the Municipalities for social services (SAD, supplementary income support), and of the Regional Health Services for health services (ADI, day centers or RSA, etc.). These different information systems should be integrated at the Regional level for families to be able to collect information on care pathways for not self-sufficient elderly people and the intensity of care of each service (Cinelli and Longo, 2021).

In Chapter 4.1 we have seen that some big players have started to offer front office family services, to guide and support families in accessing and attending services, and counseling services that offer operational or psychological counseling services for families in support of the management of not self-sufficient. The Public LTC should widen its offer in front office and counseling services both for making families aware of the LTC offers and to direct them into the solution more suited to the elderly's conditions.

Moreover, a unified Regional Information System would allow the Government to be aware of the number of beneficiaries of LTC programs and to identify for each individual the INPS/Regional/Municipality/ASLs services he or she is benefiting from.

3. Adequate Urban and Housing settings

The SHAP analysis of the variable "Urban population (% of the total population)" shows that elderly have worst living conditions in Urban Areas. This can be explained by the fact that in Rural Areas the phenomenon of Cohabitation is more common – indeed in "capital regions often recorded some of the highest concentrations of single-person households, while the lowest proportions were generally recorded in more rural areas"

(Eurostat: People in the EU - statistics on household and family structures, 2018) – and by the fact that as noted in Chapter 1.3 “those who live alone or in institutions have generally higher mortality rates than those living with their spouse or other family members”.

This brings to light the need for cities to adapt: 1) their Urban setting, and 2) their Housing conditions to the needs of the elderly.

I. Urban Aging: Age-friendly Cities

The OECD Ageing in Cities Report (2015) concludes that aging trends are different between metropolitan and non-metropolitan areas: in large urban areas the older population is growing faster than the total population. In developed regions and countries within the European Union rural areas approach or exceed urban areas in life satisfaction (Easterlin R.A. et al, 2011; Sørensen J.F.L et al., 2014). Therefore, cities must ensure the elderly’s inclusion and full access to urban spaces, structures, and services.

An age-friendly city has good mobility (such as walkability, use of public transport), it has good safety and security conditions, and it facilitates social interaction to foster a sense of local community where older people are empowered (Buffel T. et al., 2018; Van Hoof J. and Boerenfijn P., 2018; Lovell S.A., 2018). “In other words: a place where older people are actively involved, valued and supported with infrastructure and services that effectively accommodate their needs” (Joost van Hoof, et al., 2018). According to the WHO (2007), the 8 building blocks for an Age-Friendly city are: Outdoor spaces and buildings, Transportation, Housing, Civic Participation and employment, Respect and social inclusion, Social participation, Communication and information, Community Support and health services.

Examples of Age-friendly cities based on the WHO definition can be found in The Netherlands and Poland and are described in detail in the paper “The Challenges of Urban Ageing: Making Cities Age-Friendly in Europe” published in 2018 by Joost van Hoof, Jan K. Kazak, Jolanta M. Perek-Białas, and Sebastiaan T. M. Peek.

II. Housing Policies for Co-Living

The house is the place where people over 65 spend most of their daily time. Most people over 60 and over 65 show the preference of wanting to stay in a home context instead of in the more traditional structures that make up the LTC offer. Moreover, with advancing age and the reduction of family members (caused by children leaving the

home of origin, widowhood, etc.), the elderly find themselves living in buildings oversized in relation to their needs, with increasing difficulty in the management of the house. Currently, there is not a connection between welfare policies and housing policies to introduce new ways of responding to the needs of elderly people who would like and could potentially remain inside social buildings but would need to receive social monitoring and assistance, and health and social services (in case of need) for a safe stay at home. These housing preferences result in the need for the definition of solutions in which the elderly can stay at home - be it their own home or shared apartment with other people - as in the case of co-housing. Senior Living and Smart homes are two examples that can be cited in this regard.

Senior Living is a solution for the elderly who are still self-sufficient but who wish to live in a more protected context than the apartment they lived in before retirement. In this housing solution elderly live in private accommodation and receive support from specialized personnel in case of need. Senior Living is often made up of multiple apartments, where the elderly live alone or as a couple, and there is a community of over 65 individuals still active and healthy, where it is therefore possible to promote socialization and maintaining an active lifestyle.

This type of service is growing rapidly both in the United States and in Europe (especially in the United Kingdom where there are 50.000 Senior Living structures and in France, Germany, and Belgium). In Italy investments in the sector reached only 1.8% of the total investments in the real estate sector (129 million euros) (Nomisma, 2019) but it is expected in the near future a growth in the investments in this solution.

4.3.2 Cash Transfers

Public expenditure for Cash transfers amounts to € 9.1 billion, almost entirely absorbed by the Accompanying Indemnity (€ 8.8 billion).

Based on OECD indication in their report “Fiscal Sustainability of Health Systems” (2015) some structural reforms should redefine the role of the public system and private system in the assistance sector, keeping the universal coverage for essential services and favor the diffusion of best practice at clinical, organizational and management level. Indeed, greater availability of resources and services does not necessarily correspond to better health conditions of the population.

Italy in 2018 had around 74% of Current Health Expenditure covered by "gghed_che" - Domestic general government health expenditure and around 24% covered by "oops_che" - Out-of-pocket expenditure. Based on the SHAP Dependence Contribution Plot of "gghed_che" and "oops_che" (Figure 21) just rising Domestic general government health expenditure alone without the reorganization of LTC Public expenditure would not increase the Healthy Aging conditions of the elderly in the country. In this Chapter are proposed 3 initiatives the Government can adopt to increase the LTC offering without a heavy impact on its finances:

1. Reorganization of Cash Resources and Allocation Criteria

Many variables in the analysis show the correlation between the economic condition and the Healthy Aging of the Elderly. The SHAP analysis of the variable "co007" - Household able to make ends meet and "thinc_m" - Household net income, show how families and elderly with a higher disposable income are easily able to cover all monthly expenses allow the elderly to have a better quality of life. Therefore, Cash Transfers play a fundamental role in the equality of living conditions and well-being of elderly with different economic and social conditions. This highlights the need to: 1) Harmonize the evaluation criteria of access to LTC Services at a Regional level, and 2) Redesign the criteria of assignment and use of the Accompaniment Allowance (IDA) to create a more balanced and egalitarian LTC system.

1. Create a Regional Evaluation unit for access to LTC Services

Each distinct welfare pillar uses different evaluation units for the access to LTC services: the INPS commission assigns the accompanying allowance (IDA), the municipalities assign SAD and supplementary income support, and local health authorities regulate access to actual services (ADI, day centers, or RSA, etc.). The various commissions should be unified into a single evaluation unit at the Regional level whose assessment of not self-sufficiency would jointly activate the entire portfolio of services of the welfare chain. The unified evaluation unit should have a direct influence on the allocation of the budgets of the different services (Cinelli and Longo, 2021). Moreover, through the organization of a Regional Information System discussed in Chapter 4.3.1, that gathers information of the LTC services each resident in the Region is benefiting from, it would be possible to create a more balanced and egalitarian system in which each individual benefits from a maximum amount of overall

Cash Transfers from IDA and "nursing checks" and "vouchers" from Regional/Municipalities/Local Health Authorities.

II. Change the Criteria for assigning and using the Accompaniment Allowance

Currently the IDA is fixed and equal to approximately € 515 per month, however, its 1.4 million beneficiaries have different health conditions and therefore different assisting needs. The IDA monetary amount should be differentiated based on actual health conditions and the type of assisting services chosen. The elderly in need should be classified into different categories based on the severity of their health conditions, and the ones belonging to higher categories of need should benefit from a higher IDA monetary amount. Moreover, among individuals belonging to the same category of health conditions the value of the money transfer could also vary based on the service finances by the IDA: if the indemnity is used to benefit from LTC Actual services the monetary value should be higher (Cinelli and Longo, 2021). This could also be an incentive for families to recur to LTC services or regularly paid caregiving instead of irregular paid caregiving. This links to Chapter 4.3.1 regarding the possibility to integrate Public Network with Private and Non-profit Offering to create a wider and more balanced Public System.

2. Out of Pocket Upgrading of Public LTC Services

Based on ISTAT data in Italy 47% of the elderly are affected by osteoarthritis or arthritis, 32% by cardiovascular problems, 25% by osteoporosis, 17% by diabetes, 6% by Parkinson or Alzheimer, 5% by neoplasms, etc. People affected by chronic conditions might need specialized medical assistance that might not be fully provided by the current LTC services. Indeed, in Chapter 4.3.1 the CERGAS SDA Bocconi analysis regarding the reasons that tend to exclude residential care are in 23% of the cases "Lack of consistency with the elderly's care needs". A possibility could be to allow families to buy additional services from Public LTC providers, in a quantitative on-topping logic or a qualitative upgrading, to complete the provision of services guaranteed by the welfare system, which are usually insufficient (Cinelli and Longo, 2021).

This would 1) grant families to benefit from upgraded Public LTC services that cover at 360° the elderly conditions and needs, resulting in an overall better Healthy Aging for the elderly, 2) favor a process of recomposition of Public resources and integration

of services, and 3) a greater development of the Public professional market on the supply side (the providers) that would need to equip for the upgraded needs.

3. Promote Private LTC Insurance

Data on the level of coverage of the use of private and informal services (paid caregivers and family support) show how the LTC system is already challenged by aging population. Insurance is often seen as a possible solution and many of the main players in the insurance sector have promoted LTC assurance policies between 2017 and 2018. The diffusion of LTC assurance policies in Italy is still not widespread, but the insurance industry could become a good partner to the public LTC sector by increasing the share of citizens reached by services and developing a private market to complement the public one.

An analysis by CERGAS SDA Bocconi of the assurance LTC products present on the Italian market highlights that: 1) The policies are in most cases complementary to health or life insurances and are not products dedicated specifically to LTC, 2) The offer is mainly characterized by monetary reimbursements and not additional health, social or social-health services, and 3) Many policies limit to 70 years the possibility to underwrite the assurance, this is necessary in assurance products based on prevention but limits heavily the number of potential users, that de-facto is restricted to adults and young elderly, in most cases still not in need of LTC assistance (Fosti and Notarnicola, 2019).

A study conducted by Barazzetta (2018) on a sample of individuals regarding the possibility of underwriting LTC policies shows that: 53.4% said they did not do it because it was too expensive, 28.2% because they don't have enough information to decide, 13.5% because they consider themselves in good health, and around 8% because they prefer to accumulate savings.

These results show that in the eyes of potential LTC assurance users the policies appear very complex, oriented towards a very distant future with a logic of prevention, and mostly based on monetary reimbursement, which makes it a not very attractive alternative compared to accumulating savings.

The Government could boost LTC insurance with tax breaks, allowing to deduct at least part of the cost of LTC assurance and the additional out-of-pocket expenses that might incur for the not self-sufficient not covered by the LTC assurance. These “fiscal

facilitations” are currently used for integrated health funds and yearly amount to 1.5 billion per year, with a “saved” cost for the National Healthcare System of 4.3 billion, as the Government saves the Healthcare costs managed by integrated health funds (through Private ambulatories and hospitals). Adopting a similar strategy for LTC insurances would: 1) Ensure good levels of health care and social care for all elderly through therapeutic paths covered and not covered by LTC services, 2) Encourage the use of Private facilities to relieve pressure on LTC public services, and 3) Reduce the risk of unsustainable out-of-pocket expenses for the elderly (this is especially meaningful for people with low income as by underwriting a LTC insurance they would receive reimbursement for all medical expenses in case of not self-sufficiency that they would not be able to cover with an out-of-pocket expense).

5. Conclusions

The aim of this Thesis was to answer two Research Questions: 1) identify the main factors that impact the Healthy Aging of the Elderly Population in European countries, and 2) provide policy suggestions to Italy to better support its Aging Population by improving the quality of life of its Elderly Population.

The first Research Question was covered in Chapters 1,2, and 3 through an introduction of the Aging Population in Europe and the World Health Organization's Healthy Aging concept to assess the quality of life of elderly population in Europe. To answer the first Research Question it was performed an analysis of individual variables from the easySHARE Database and macroeconomic variables from the World Bank Data from 28 European Countries using 3 models: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Light Gradient Boosting Machine. The models were then evaluated through the 4 key metrics to evaluate a Classification Problem: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F-1 Score. The Light Gradient Boosting Machine was the most accurate and balanced model and therefore its results were analyzed with the SHAP values. Based on the Light Gradient Boosting Machine's findings 20 variables (regarding physical and mental health, frequency of vigorous activities and medical visits, urban settings, economic conditions, and public and private out-of-pocket health expenditure) resulted to have an impact on the Healthy Aging in Europe. Based on the findings of the first Research Question it was possible to formulate policy suggestions for Italy to answer the second Research Question.

The second Research Question was covered in Chapter 4 through an overview of the Italian Public Healthcare and Social Services for the elderly (mainly offered by Long Term Care services), the coverage rate of Long Term Care Services, and the Private Caregiving market. Based on the Italian services for the elderly and the findings of the Light Gradient Boosting Machine model, it was possible to formulate six policy suggestions to better support Aging Population in Italy by improving the quality of life of its Elderly Population. The six policy suggestions are: 1) Invest in MicroServices and Technology to support Physical and Mental Health, 2) Reorganize the Public LTC Network: Integrate Private and Non-profit offering and Create a Unified Information System, 3) Adequate Urban and Housing settings, 4) Reorganization of Cash Resources and Allocation Criteria, 5) Out of Pocket Upgrading of Public LTC Services, and 6) Promote Private LTC Insurance.

The analysis of the Healthy Aging in Italy compared to other European countries highlighted that only 33,42% of its elderly population is considered to be in “Good Aging Conditions”, with Italy being one among the worst countries in these terms. Moreover, the overview of the Italian Long Term Care Services highlighted a fragmented situation with an offer that is insufficient for the needs of the Italian elderly population.

Therefore, the six policy suggestions shall be interpreted as a unique proposal that aims at reorganizing the Italian offering, without a heavy impact on the public expenditure, to increase the number of users by widening and integrating the Public, Private and Non-Profit Offering to better cover, ideally at 360°, the needs of the elderly population in Italy.

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